

Report on academic integrity awareness and Open Science recognition levels in Ukraine (2021-2023)

Open Practices, Transparency and Integrity for Modern Academia

Version 1.0
PUBLIC

This report summarizes results from three consecutive surveys on Open Science and academic integrity attitudes and behaviours spanning the years 2021 to 2023. The survey data includes a total of 24,705 total responses from members of the student body and academic community of Ukrainian higher education institutions.

Programme: Erasmus+

Key Action: Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices

Action Type: Capacity building in higher education

Project Reference: 618940-EPP-1-2020-1-UA-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP

This document is licensed under a Creative Commons

[Attribution 4.0 International Licence](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) (CC BY 4.0)

With the support of the
Erasmus+ Programme
of the European Union

Document Description

Report on academic integrity awareness and Open Science recognition levels in Ukraine (2021-2023)

Report on academic integrity awareness and Open Science recognition levels in Ukraine (2021-2023)			
Due date:	1 October 2024	Actual delivery date:	1 October 2024
Nature of document	Report	Version	1.0
Dissemination level	Public		
Lead partner	TU Graz		
Authors	Eva Kormann, Thomas Klebel, Pavlo Zhezhnych, Oleksandr Berezko, Tony Ross-Hellauer		
Reviewers	Iryna Kuchma		

Revision History

Issue	Item	Comments	Author/Reviewer
V0.5	Draft Version	First draft	Eva Kormann, Thomas Klebel, Tony Ross-Hellauer
V0.6	Revised Draft	Review and editing	Pavlo Zhezhnych, Oleksandr Berezko, Iryna Kuchma
V1.0	Finalization	Integration of feedback, revisions, final formatting	Eva Kormann, Thomas Klebel, Tony Ross-Hellauer

The OPTIMA consortium considers this report a preprint of the upcoming publication of this material in a peer reviewed Open Access publishing venue. This will be done after collecting feedback from stakeholders.

Original data and materials are available from Berezko et al. (2021; 2022, 2024). Translated data and analysis code are available from Kormann et al. (2024).

The European Commission's support for the production of this publication does not constitute an endorsement of the contents, which reflect the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Table of Contents

Document Description.....	1
Table of Contents	2
Acknowledgments	4
Executive Summary	5
1. Introduction.....	7
2. Background.....	8
2.1. Open Science, Research and Academic Integrity: Aims and Policies	8
2.1.1. Open Science	8
2.1.2. Research and Academic Integrity	9
2.2. Existing Knowledge on Attitudes and Behaviours to OS, Research and Academic Integrity	10
2.3. Situation in Ukraine	12
3. Methods	15
3.1. Study Design	15
3.2. Instrument and Administration	15
3.3. Population of Interest	16
3.4. Ethical Considerations	17
3.5. Analysis.....	17
4. Results	19
4.1. Demographic Characteristics.....	19
4.2. Investigation of “ <i>don’t know</i> ” Responses	20
4.3. Open Science	22
4.3.1. Overview.....	22
4.3.2. Development over Time	24
4.3.3. Comparison by Academic Role	25
4.4. Reporting and Academic Integrity.....	28
4.4.1. Overview.....	28
4.4.2. Development over Time	31
4.4.3. Comparison by Academic Role	33
4.5. Education.....	35
4.5.1. Overview.....	35
4.5.2. Development over Time	37
4.5.3. Comparison by Academic Role	38

4.6.	Institution/Administration	40
4.6.1.	Overview.....	40
4.6.2.	Development over Time	42
4.6.3.	Comparison by Academic Role	43
5.	Discussion	45
5.1.	Awareness and Knowledge	45
5.2.	Attitudes and Behaviours	46
5.2.1.	Open Science	46
5.2.2.	Reporting and Academic Integrity.....	48
5.2.3.	Education.....	49
5.2.4.	Institution/Administration	50
5.3.	Summary.....	51
5.4.	Limitations	51
5.5.	Recommendations.....	52
6.	Bibliography.....	53
7.	Appendices	61
A.	Survey Instrument	61
B.	Additional Demographic Characteristics	63
C.	Additional Results and Figures	70

Acknowledgments

This report is based on data collected through three surveys on Open Science and academic integrity conducted at Ukrainian higher education institutions. These surveys were developed and conducted by multiple OPTIMA team members in great collaboration. We especially want to acknowledge the contributions of:

- Artyukhov, Artem
- Chernov, Anatolii
- Cophignon, Auréa
- Degtyarova, Iryna
- Herasymchuk, Halyna
- Khadzhynov, Illya
- Krakovska, Svitlana
- Krasnoshchok, Oleksandr
- Mozolevych, Grygoriy
- Oriekhova, Tetyana
- Pnyovska, Oksana
- Reichmann, Stefan
- Tsiatkovska, Albina
- Wodo, Wojciech
- Zhyltsova, Svitlana

We additionally thank everyone who supported the distribution of the surveys at OPTIMA partner institutions and nationally and everyone who took the time to participate.

Finally, we are very grateful to Iryna Kuchma for her contributions to developing and conducting the survey, as well as for reviewing this report and providing valuable comments.

Executive Summary

Background:

This report presents the results of a large-scale survey on Open Science (OS) and academic integrity in Ukraine. OS describes a movement aiming to make science more open, transparent, accessible and collaborative. Academic integrity refers to principles of responsible behaviours in relation to all academic practice, including the conduct of research, as well as student behaviour in the context of education. In Ukraine, great efforts have been made to promote both OS and academic integrity. This survey was conducted in the course of the OPTIMA project, which specifically aims to improve higher education and academic integrity, e.g., by raising OS awareness and establishing more OS practices. Despite difficult circumstances caused by pandemic and war, encouraging progress has been made in Ukraine, such as approving the National Open Science Plan in 2022. Still, there has so far been no large-scale systematic investigations of awareness, attitudes and behaviours until this study. This survey aims to fill this gap and provide benchmarks for future monitoring.

Methodology:

The survey was conducted over three years (2021-2023). It consisted of two main channels of recruitment: within the OPTIMA partner institutions, and a national survey. Recruitment was broad, targeting the entire academic body of Ukrainian higher education institutions (HEIs). Each survey contained demographic questions and the same 38 content-related questions across years, of which 24 were on agreement with certain statements (attitudes), and 14 on the frequency of certain questionable practices (behaviours).

Results:

Across the three waves, there were 24,705 total complete responses. Most responses came from the national survey, with a diversity of fields and types of institutions. The 2022 wave had the largest sample, with the highest share of students and respondents without publication/peer review/work experience. Compared to the overall gender distribution in Ukrainian HEIs, women made up the majority of respondents in the survey, with more than 60% of responses.

We observed a high share of “don’t know” responses for many questions, with more than 50% “don’t know” responses for particular items. On attitudes towards OS, we observed that the majority of respondents agreed with the statements on OS (except for one), indicating that OS practices are generally perceived as relevant and desirable. On research integrity, agreement with statements on responsible reporting practices and academic integrity was generally very high. Major research misconduct was reported as less common compared to more minor QRPs (e.g., around citations), but still quite prevalent, with 38.8% and 43.5% reporting plagiarism and fabrication to occur at their HEI (at least rarely), respectively. For all QRPs, less than 20% report that they occur very often or frequently (8.4% for plagiarism and 9.3% for fabrication). Less than half report that they occur at least sometimes. On education, we similarly found high levels of agreement, with at least 75% of respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing to each of the four items. 94.3% of respondents agreed with the statement that students should understand what constitutes inappropriate academic behaviour and report it to the appropriate authorities. On questionable practices by institutions or the HEI’s administration, respondents rated them to take place “frequently” or “very often” in 6.2% to 21.0% across the five included items. The item with the highest reported frequency concerns university administrations accusing and punishing whistleblowers of academic integrity violations, with 21.0% responding “very often” or “frequently”, and 18.0% responding with “sometimes”.

Discussion:

Overall, we observed very positive attitudes towards OS and principles of academic integrity. Over the years 2021-2023, there appears to not have been very pronounced developments, with responses only changing slightly overall. Group differences often followed similar patterns, with students and research staff, and university administrators and faculty, respectively, being more similar in their responses. Often, opinions diverged along the question of who would be more affected, or responsible for implementation. For instance, students agreed less with their theses being published OA, while research staff were least open to OPR practices, and vice versa. Reports on behaviours also differ between groups, indicating different levels of awareness or distinct reporting tendencies, e.g., with responses by university administrators painting a more positive picture.

Our findings should be interpreted in the context of the pandemic and war. The increased prevalence of distance learning due to COVID-19 may have reduced opportunities for informal learning about the practices of peers, contributing to the high “don’t know” responses observed. The war has created additional disruptions, including displacement and changes in institutional structures, which likely affect both awareness and reported behaviours. In this context, the observed differences in the frequency of academic misconduct might reflect both actual behavioural changes and increased awareness or scrutiny during challenging circumstances. For example, the rise in reported misconduct in 2023 could be due to heightened awareness or better monitoring by institutions as they adapted to ongoing challenges.

1. Introduction

This study analyses and reports on survey data (24,705 total responses) collected between 2021 and 2023 to investigate attitudes and behaviours regarding Open Science, research and academic integrity amongst students, researchers and support staff primarily at Ukrainian higher education institutions (HEIs).

There is broad consensus that academic research processes will benefit from greater transparency and integrity of research. Open Science (OS), research integrity and academic integrity are somewhat overlapping concepts relevant to this end. OS can be described both as a movement and a set of practices with the aim of conducting and assessing research in an open, transparent, accessible and collaborative manner (Vicente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018). Research integrity refers to the responsible conduct of research aiming to prevent practices among researchers that endanger its validity and trustworthiness (Bouter, 2020). This concept is related to OS, sharing the goal of traceable and verifiable research (Haven et al., 2022). Academic integrity is sometimes used to refer to ethical or moral principles guiding responsible, fair and respectful conduct among students related to the educational context. However, the term also refers more broadly to all aspects of academic practices (Macfarlane et al., 2014), encompassing the more narrowly defined concept of research integrity following this understanding.

This work is undertaken in the framework of the OPTIMA project, an EC Erasmus+ funded effort (2021-2025) to promote Open Science practices in Ukraine to improve the quality of national higher education services. OPTIMA's priorities include engaging disadvantaged academic communities of displaced Ukrainian universities, focusing on climate change as well as inclusivity by means of modern information technologies.

This study supports these aims by presenting analysis of the data regarding overall attitudes and behaviours, and of changes over time. Our interpretation of these results also takes into consideration the impacts of the global COVID-19 pandemic and the full-scale Russia's invasion of Ukraine within the time-period covered by the survey. We close by presenting our interpretations of the implications of these findings for future policy and practice in Ukraine.

This report is structured to first present essential contextual knowledge regarding OS and research and academic integrity, also reviewing existing literature on awareness, attitudes and behaviours surrounding these issues. We then give an overview over the situation in Ukraine and efforts that are being taken towards OS and research and academic integrity. Subsequently, we report on the methodology and the results of the survey and discuss them in the context of the literature with attention to limitations and recommendations.

2. Background

2.1. Open Science, Research and Academic Integrity: Aims and Policies

2.1.1. Open Science

The concept of OS is lacking a generally accepted formal definition, but revolves around the idea of an open, transparent, accessible and collaborative conduct and assessment of research (Vicente-Saez & Martinez-Fuentes, 2018). It can be described as both a movement and a set of practices. After reviewing the literature on OS, Fecher and Friesike (2014) describe five different schools of thought with different aims and focus:

- Infrastructure School: create openly available infrastructure for scientists
- Public School: make science accessible for the broad public
- Measurement School: develop alternative ways to measure scientific impact
- Democratic School: address inequalities in access to knowledge
- Pragmatic School: increase efficiency of knowledge production

More recently, UNESCO have attempted to form consensus around the definition of OS as “an inclusive construct that combines various movements and practices aiming to make multilingual scientific knowledge openly available, accessible and reusable for everyone, to increase scientific collaborations and sharing of information for the benefits of science and society, and to open the processes of scientific knowledge creation, evaluation and communication to societal actors beyond the traditional scientific community.” (UNESCO, 2021)

One of the key practices of OS is Open Access publishing (OA). This describes the practice of making academic publications accessible to the public free of charge (Suber, 2012). Publishing preprints is a related practice where research results are disseminated openly before peer review and publication (Soderberg et al., 2020). Other practices include openly sharing research materials, such as Open Data and Open Code, also following FAIR (i.e. findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable) principles (Easterbrook, 2014; Murray-Rust, 2008; Sciences, 2003; Wilkinson et al., 2016). Open Peer Review (OPR) aims at achieving a more open research assessment and subsumes multiple open practices within the peer review process, e.g., open identities, openly accessible reports or open participation by a wider community (Ross-Hellauer, 2017).

In addition to researchers, government bodies, funders, HEIs, and other key stakeholders, several international organisations have become concerned with OS. The OECD published their Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data From Public Funding in 2007 and further aims to promote OS (OECD, 2015, 2021). In 2021, the UNESCO published their recommendations on Open Science, the source of the above UNESCO definition above, encouraging their adoption by member states. As well as offering a common definition of OS with focus on access, collaborations and societal benefit, they also formulate potential steps for their member states including: investments in infrastructure and education, creating respective policies, and shaping a culture of OS (UNESCO, 2021; UNESCO & Canadian National Commission for UNESCO, 2022).

The European Commission (EC) has made OS a priority and identified several areas for action: incentives, removal of barriers, policies, infrastructure and embedding in society (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission), 2016b). Subsequently, respective policies were implemented in the EU programmes for research funding. While the focus in Horizon 2020 lay primarily on mandating OA publishing

(with some piloting and roll-out of Open Data policies), the OS policy was extended in Horizon Europe. There, OA publishing and sharing of data “as openly as possible, as closed as necessary” following FAIR principles is mandatory, with further practices such as sharing of preprints and further research materials and OPR recommended (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission), 2016a, 2017, 2024). The EU also provides OS infrastructure through their publishing platform Open Research Europe that follows OA and OPR principles, and the European Open Science Cloud for FAIR sharing of digital research materials (Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission), 2024).

Substantial academic, societal, and economic progress is expected from furthering OS, such as more productive research, economic growth, more progress towards achieving the SDGs, etc. Although not all claimed impacts of OS have been investigated formally (Cole et al., 2024; Klebel et al., 2024) and current developments in OS also come with risks of unintended consequences (Ross-Hellauer et al., 2022), many nations see great benefit in that outweigh possible downsides.

2.1.2. Research and Academic Integrity

Research integrity refers to principles aiming at making research more valid and trustworthy (Bouter, 2020; Haven et al., 2022). Researchers who were interviewed about their understanding of research integrity defined it as honesty, transparency, and objectivity, with truth being the main aspect (Shaw & Satalkar, 2018). Research integrity on the one hand aims to reduce practices that are detrimental to these principles (Bouter, 2020; Gopalakrishna, Riet, et al., 2022; Haven et al., 2022). These include fabrication, falsification and plagiarism (FFP) which are seen as major misconduct. However, questionable research practices (QRPs), which are in isolation smaller violations of the principles of research integrity, are assumed to be in sum more detrimental because of their substantially higher prevalence. Many relatively common practices can be termed to fall under the umbrella of QRPs, such as omitting study details, selective citations or not submitting negative results for publication. On the opposite end of the spectrum, the concept of responsible research practices (RRPs) is highly relevant, describing behaviours such as detailed record keeping or expert consultations (Bouter, 2020; Gopalakrishna, Riet, et al., 2022; Gopalakrishna, Wicherts, et al., 2022; Haven et al., 2022). Research integrity can therefore not only be seen as the absence of FFP and QRPs, but also as integral behaviour going beyond that. Although research so far has mostly focused on FFP and QRPs and how to minimise them, more weight in meta-research is being put on the question how to promote RRP recently (Gopalakrishna, Wicherts, et al., 2022).

Important documents on the topic of research integrity are the Singapore Statement on Research Integrity (Resnik & Shamoo, 2011) and the Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers (Moher et al., 2020). Both were formulated in the context of a respective World Conference on Research Integrity and include principles for the responsible conduct of research and responsibilities for researchers. The European Code of Conduct also defines the principles of reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability and additionally lists good research practices vs. those that violate research integrity (ALLEA - All European Academies, 2023). Many (national) initiatives are concerned with research integrity and respective research assessment (Bouter, 2020). Key stakeholders in this area are also the research institutions, with the ability to decide how much to educate PhD students (Abdi et al., 2021) and to issue written statements on integral behaviour in research. Half of respondents on a survey in Europe and North America reported their institution to have such a statement (Allum et al., 2023).

Academic integrity is a broader term that is often used to specifically refer to student behaviour in an academic educational setting. However, it is also understood as a term encompassing the integrity of all of academic practice, therefore including research integrity in addition to academic education (Macfarlane et al., 2014). Dishonest practices such as plagiarism or incorrect citations are threats to both research integrity and the integrity of student behaviour. However, some practices are more specific to the educational context, such as cheating on exams, which is mostly regulated and sanctioned by the respective institution (Zhao et al., 2024). In the context of this study, academic integrity is interpreted in its broad sense, including research integrity and behaviours in education.

2.2. Existing Knowledge on Attitudes and Behaviours to OS, Research and Academic Integrity

As researchers shape the conduct of research through their individual behaviours, it is of great interest to assess their awareness, attitudes and behaviours regarding OS and research integrity. In a survey of UK psychology PhD students, respondents were quite mixed in their confidence that they could explain OS concepts, with some indicating that they have not heard of OS at all (Pownall et al., 2023). Specific practices, such as Data Management Plans (DMPs) are also quite unknown, with less than half of respondents being aware of the practice in a survey on Open Data (Digital Science et al., 2023). A survey that covers early-career researchers from across Europe and all disciplines has found that awareness generally increases with career seniority (Berezko, Medina, et al., 2021).

Researchers generally report quite positive attitudes towards OS practices, e.g., that they have more hopes compared to fears related to it (Abele-Brehm et al., 2019). Some OS practices are perceived more positively than others. Across multiple different surveys, OA is supported the most, followed by Open Data (Digital Science et al., 2023; Harpe, 2024; Ross-Hellauer et al., 2017). OPR is perceived less positively, with researchers appearing hesitant to make related aspects common practice (Digital Science et al., 2023; Ross-Hellauer et al., 2017). Some studies suggest that publishing preprints is a less favourably viewed practice (Digital Science et al., 2023; Harpe, 2024; Ni & Waltman, 2024), but another survey on preprints reports more positive attitudes (Soderberg et al., 2020). Cross-disciplinary investigations of attitudes have additionally revealed differences, both between disciplines (Digital Science et al., 2023) and when comparing subdisciplines, e.g., within social sciences (Christensen et al., 2020; Ferguson et al., 2023). Findings like these emphasise the relevance of the disciplinary context in attitudes towards OS.

Regarding behaviours, Ferguson et al. (2023), for instance, reported an increase in adoption across all surveyed OS practices within social sciences, with 87% of respondents already having used at least one OS practice. However, how many researchers actually engage depends again on the OS practice. Findings suggest that OA publishing is the most prevalent practice (Harpe, 2024; Pownall et al., 2023), but the role of disciplinary context and different modes of inquiry about these behaviours complicate comparisons across studies.

A multitude of studies observe an attitude-behaviour gap, meaning that even though they find positive attitudes towards OS, specific behaviours are only observed less often (Harpe, 2024; Rowley et al., 2017; Schöpfel et al., 2016; Soderberg et al., 2020). When researchers are asked about their reasons for not engaging in OS, they list aspects such as lack of time, lack of training and education, lack of guidance and support, and lack of incentives (Digital Science et al., 2023; Pownall et al., 2023; Zečević et al., 2021). They perceive their research culture and associated norms to put less emphasis on OS. While perceived

engagement of colleagues with OS practices might be underestimated at times (Christensen et al., 2020; Ferguson et al., 2023), expectations from supervisors and institutions are often experienced as a barrier to OS (Pownall et al., 2023; Ross-Hellauer et al., 2024).

Until now, a lot of research on research integrity has attempted to estimate the prevalence of research misconduct (FFP) and QRPs, with awareness, attitudes, or RRP less investigated. Prior to research integrity training, 49% of early-career researchers reported a good understanding of the meaning and value of research integrity in an Italian study (Mabou Tagne et al., 2020). In terms of attitudes, although meta-researchers believe that QRPs are in sum more detrimental to the validity of research compared to FFP (Bouter, 2020), Norwegian researchers believe FFP to be much more severe than QRPs (Kaiser et al., 2021). In a survey among PhD graduates at a university in Oslo, 18% indicated that they found at least one of the listed practices acceptable (Hofmann & Holm, 2019). The practices that are considered acceptable also depend strongly on the disciplinary context (Ravn & Sørensen, 2021). Attitudes among Norwegian PhD candidates do not appear to have changed much over the course of completing their PhD, nor to differ between cohorts ten years apart (Hofmann et al., 2023; Hofmann & Holm, 2019). Attitudes towards research integrity, however, are generally in line with its principles, with almost all respondents from a Belgian university agreeing that they value research integrity (De Peuter et al., 2024). Support is also very high for measures intended to increase research integrity (Allum et al., 2023).

Surveys are the predominant methods used to obtain estimates about the prevalence of FFP and QRPs. However, different approaches to phrasing questions are used, e.g., with different recall periods, different lists of practices or own vs. observed practices, with self-reporting always bearing the risk of underreporting because of social desirability (Schneider et al., 2024). The discrepancies in numbers reported across studies might therefore be rooted in methodological differences. Numbers again depend on the disciplinary context (Ravn & Sørensen, 2021) and the type of practice. Although FFP see a lot of reports and media attention (Armond et al., 2021; Bouter, 2020), studies on these issues actually report very low prevalences. Numbers range from 0.2% self-reported engagement with these practices to around 4% (Gopalakrishna, Riet, et al., 2022; Hofmann & Holm, 2019; Kaiser et al., 2021; Xie et al., 2021). QRPs are reported as occurring more frequently. The proportion of respondents reporting to engage in at least one QRP ranges from 12.5% (Xie et al., 2021) to around half (Gopalakrishna, Riet, et al., 2022; Kaiser et al., 2021) to up to 90% (Schneider et al., 2024).

Researchers that are more junior engage more often in QRPs (Gopalakrishna, Riet, et al., 2022; Schneider et al., 2024). Reported lack of knowledge on written policies or resources at university might play a role in this (De Peuter et al., 2024; Hofmann et al., 2023). However, lack of support from supervisors, pressure from others, publication pressure, and the research culture are also named as general barriers towards avoiding QRPs and engaging in RRP (De Peuter et al., 2024; Gopalakrishna, Riet, et al., 2022; Hofmann & Holm, 2019; Schneider et al., 2024).

The perceived barriers towards OS and research integrity are in line with review, promotion, and tenure policies and institutions that focus on quantification and therefore incentivise problematic practices instead of OS and responsible research practices (Pontika et al., 2022). Because of this, researchers have called for a change in culture and efforts from institutions, funders, and publishers in order to promote OS and the responsible conduct of research (Bouter, 2020; Nosek, 2019).

To provide a more complete picture of academic integrity as we understand it here, reports on student misconduct are also of interest for this study. Investigations of students' awareness of academic integrity issues show that although students recognize its importance, they are not clear in detail about which practices are considered violations. Students had trouble assessing more nuanced issues around citations and were often not entirely aware of what their institution's policy covered (Childers & Bruton, 2016; Liut et al., 2024). In two surveys among Australian universities, responses showed that there is room for improvement at these institutions to make principles of academic integrity more salient (Campbell & Waddington, 2024). While students are often not aware of principles and their institution's policy on academic integrity, cheating in graded activities is generally perceived as less acceptable by students compared to non-graded activities (Molnar & Kletke, 2012).

Two important developments in this area have occurred in recent years. On the one hand, distance learning increased in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. Cheating appears to have increased during the now more common online examinations (Erçin Kamburoğlu & Razi, 2024; Newton & Essex, 2024). The rise of generative artificial intelligence (AI) also poses new challenges for the definition and assessment of student misconduct, with students increasingly using such tools without seeing it as a breach of integrity (Gruenhagen et al., 2024). While student behaviour is an important aspect of academic integrity and interconnected with aspects of research integrity and OS, it has mostly been addressed separately from these more research-related issues.

2.3. Situation in Ukraine

In Ukraine, great efforts have been made by universities and research institutes, publishing OA journals (over 450 indexed in DOAJ) and setting up a multitude of institutional repositories (*Directory of Open Access Journals – DOAJ*, 2024; 'National Repository of Academic Texts', 2024). Several measures are also being taken on a national level to promote OS (EOSC Association, 2022; Kaliuzhna & Hauschke, 2024). In more recent years, Ukraine has focussed more on its participation in the European research and innovation spaces, has implemented the "National Repository of Academic Texts" and signed the agreement with the EU to participate in Horizon Europe. Among other developments, the National Open Science Plan has been approved in 2022 despite the wartime difficulties (EOSC Association, 2022; Government of Ukraine, 2022; Kaliuzhna & Hauschke, 2024). This plan stipulates integration of OS into all national sciences, research, education, technology and innovation policies, strategies and action plans. It also supports repository developments, encourages citizen science, drives research assessment reform and supports OS skills and competences building (Government of Ukraine, 2022). OPTIMA team members were involved in developing the National Open Science Plan and its project outputs were used to inform it.

Several non-governmental initiatives have been formed recently in Ukraine to promote OS. The Erasmus+ funded project OPTIMA is one of them with the aim to improve the quality of higher education services through OS practices (*OPTIMA | Lviv Polytechnic National University*, 2021). Open4UA is also funded through Erasmus+ and follows OPTIMA with its aims to achieve modernization and EU integration through OS and to reform research assessment (*Open4UA | Lviv Polytechnic National University*, 2023). To support the implementation of the National Open Science Plan the "Institute for Open Science and Innovation (INOSI)" was also founded in 2023 to create a network of experts on OS (*About Institute for Open Science and Innovation | Institute for Open Science and Innovation*, 2023).

Regarding academic integrity, Ukraine implemented new legislation to improve higher education in 2014. This law mostly aims at reducing plagiarism and covers other dishonest behaviour only indirectly for academic

staff and not at all for students. The main responsibility for monitoring academic dishonesty lies with several institutions, such as the National Quality Assurance Agency and the Academic Councils of the HEIs (OECD, 2017). In June 2024, the new draft law on academic integrity defining the basic principles of ensuring academic integrity in education and research passed the first reading in the Parliament (Zhelnin & Havryliuk, 2024).

In recent years, Ukrainian HEIs, their students and staff have found themselves in unusual and challenging circumstances. With the lockdowns issued at the start of the COVID-19 pandemic in early 2020, HEIs previously relying on traditional face-to-face teaching methods were mandated to quickly shift to distance learning. Experience with online teaching had been limited up until this point and the transition was complicated by technical, organisational, psychological, and motivational barriers. However, teaching staff and students were quick to take up new methods and tools of teaching and learning. Increased emphasis was put on the use of digital information technologies (Shevchenko et al., 2024; Stukalo & Simakhova, 2020).

Following Russian aggression in Donetsk and Luhansk oblasts, and on the Crimean Peninsula in 2014, several HEIs were displaced and had to move from occupied to government-controlled territories. With the outbreak of the full-scale war in 2022, a second wave of displacement occurred, with some HEIs relocating for the second time within eight years. Although these displaced HEIs managed to build resilience and continue their work, e.g., through distance learning and digitization of processes, loss of human capital with reduced numbers in both staff and students was substantial (Porkuian et al., 2023; Zakharova & Prodanova, 2023). While human capital at universities is very important for post-war recovery, promoting OS is also thought to increase research capacity and aid in post-war reconstruction (Lugovyi et al., 2022).

Investigations of attitudes and behaviours in the context of OS and academic integrity in Ukraine are limited. A survey covering early-career researchers from across Europe and all disciplines found that awareness and positive attitudes towards OS and related practices were most pronounced in Western Europe, followed by northern, central, and southern Europe. Researchers in eastern Europe (including Ukraine) were least aware of OS (Berezko, Medina, et al., 2021). This also suggests that results from studies in other countries are limited in their generalizability to Ukraine.

In a small survey among four departments of one technical university, none of the (unspecified number of) respondents had heard of the term “Open Science” before (Vlashenko et al., 2021). Preceding training workshops on working with data and the internationalisation of research, 56 participating scientific and pedagogical workers were surveyed in 2023. Of those, 80% were aware of the concept of “Open Science” and the National Open Science Plan without knowing it in detail, while 15% had never heard of it. FAIR principles were unfamiliar to 42% of participants (Koblianska & Kostetska, 2023). In terms of behaviour, a study on the development of OA publishing from 2012 to 2021 showed that 71.5% of investigated articles were openly available, most of them in national journals (Kaliuzhna & Hauschke, 2024).

In a Ukrainian survey, 39% of students report that students at their department engage at least sometimes in cheating on exams, while 45% report that students at their department are not authoring their written assignments independently, at least sometimes. Cheat sheets are the most common type of cheating on exams as reported by students and teachers, followed by using the internet to look up answers (OECD, 2017). In another small survey at two Ukrainian HEIs, students report very high prevalence for cheating on exams and plagiarism on reports, with the majority reporting to engage in such behaviours themselves. At the same time respondents report that these violations are detected rarely. Additionally, surveyed students seemed

to lack understanding of dishonest practices (Luniachek et al., 2020). These violations of academic integrity are facilitated through a lack of clear and generally accepted ethical norms, regulations and enforcement, among other structural enablers, and are a major problem in the Ukrainian higher education system (OECD, 2017). The transition to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic has additionally solidified some of these issues (Duliba et al., 2022).

These findings indicate a lack of awareness on topics of OS and a critical level of academic dishonesty in Ukrainian HEIs. However, there is a lack of up-to-date large-scale data, with the conditions of martial law complicating the conduct of such investigations (Lugovyi et al., 2022). This study therefore brings important and novel insights into attitudes and behaviours at Ukrainian HEIs through its large-scale and repeated investigation of the matter, spanning multiple years and serving as a reference for future investigations.

3. Methods

3.1. Study Design

This online study was conducted in both a national survey, where members of the student academic body of any HEI were recruited broadly throughout Ukraine, and institutional surveys with more targeted recruitment. Each OPTIMA partner HEI conducted a survey separate from the national survey. These HEIs are the following:

- Lviv Polytechnic National University (LPU)
- Sumy State University (SumDU)
- Vasyl' Stus Donetsk National University (DonNU)
- Lutsk National Technical University (LutskNTU)

The survey was repeated three times, in 2021, 2022, and 2023. Since it cannot be reconstructed from the data whether individuals responded repeatedly or whether new individuals took part each year, this survey cannot be clearly categorised as either cross-sectional or longitudinal, but rather constitutes a mix of both.

3.2. Instrument and Administration

The language of the survey instrument was Ukrainian. After giving informed consent to participate, the respondents were presented questions about demographic characteristics. Subsequently, a variety of questions were presented on OS, reporting, academic integrity, education and institutional/administrative processes. These were on the one hand phrased to inquire about agreement with specific statements: "To what extent do you agree with the following statements?". Respondents could respond with "strongly agree", "rather agree", "rather disagree", or "strongly disagree". Other items inquired about the occurrence of certain events at the respondents' respective institutions by asking "Based on your personal experience, how often do such cases occur in your higher education institution?", with the options to respond with "very often", "frequently", "sometimes", "rarely, or "never" (see Table 1 and Table A. 1 for all statements in detail). All questions were mandatory, except the second section of agreement questions (part 4). However, all content-related questions and the clarity question could be answered with "don't know".

Table 1. Sections of the survey instrument by topic with number of included questions.

	Topic	Number of Questions
1	Demographic characteristics	7
2	Agreement with statements on reporting and academic integrity, and education	9
3	Frequency of misconduct regarding reporting and academic integrity, education, and administration at respective HEI	14
4	Agreement with statements on OS, reporting, academic integrity, education and administration	15
5	Clarity question	1

Content-related questions were consistent across years and national and institutional surveys. Survey instruments differed slightly regarding the demographic questions. National surveys contained questions on the location and type of the respondent's HEI which the institutional surveys did not. Only in 2022, more questions were added to the demographic characteristics section, three inquiring about displacement, refugee status and current whereabouts of the respondent, and two about displacement and status of the HEI (but those only in the national survey). That same year another question was added at the end of all surveys about whether the respondents were aware of the recently approved National Open Science Plan. Therefore, the minimum number of questions lay at 46, the maximum at 54. The full instruments are openly accessible together with the datasets (Berezko et al., 2022, 2024; Berezko, Reichmann, et al., 2021). The survey took a median of nine minutes to complete across all respondents.

The questionnaire was developed within a working group consisting of OPTIMA consortium members and several external experts. The instrument itself (MS Forms) was developed by Oleksandr Berezko. Technical pre-testing was done among the survey developers.

Microsoft Forms was used as the online platform for survey administration for its GDPR compliance. Recruitment emails were sent out with the link on the first day of the surveys being active. Throughout the timeframe of the surveys, reminders were sent out by multiple organisations, in the case of the institutional surveys internally, e.g., via websites and mailing lists. Surveys were active at these times:

- 2021: December 13-30 (simultaneous institutional and national surveys)
- 2022: November 7 - December 4 (simultaneous institutional and national surveys)
- 2023: November 15 - December 3 (institutional), December 4 - December 31 (national)

3.3. Population of Interest

The population of interest for this study was the entire student body and academic community of Ukrainian HEIs. Institutional surveys were disseminated strictly in their target HEIs (OPTIMA partner institutions) via various channels: university websites, internal mailing lists and information systems, at internal meetings, and through word of mouth. For the national survey, respondents were recruited through multiple channels:

- Official letters with an invitation to fill in and disseminate the survey to all Ukrainian HEIs from the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine (MESU);
- MESU mailing lists and social media;
- Mailing lists and social media of the National Agency for Higher Education Quality Assurance;
- Mailing lists and social media of the Young Scientists Council at the MESU;
- OPTIMA project's social media;
- Personal contacts of the consortium members.

To check the extent to which the target population was reached and responded to the survey, comparisons were made with numbers from the Ukraine State Statistics Service on HEI students and scientific and pedagogical staff. One caveat to this is that the official statistics include numbers on scientific and pedagogical staff of HEIs which might not include administrative and support staff, as was done in this survey. According to these statistics, Ukrainian HEIs had 1,046,669 students and 125,360 staff in 2021. This compares to 5,158 self-identified students and 4,045 self-identified staff responding to the survey in 2021, constituting an estimated 0.5% and 3.2% of the respective total population of interest. In 2022, an estimated 0.6% of Ukrainian students and 2.6% of HEI staff responded, while the sample from 2023 amounts to 0.3% of students

and 2.3% of staff. Gender distributions were also compared between this sample and official HEI statistics. This sample included a higher proportion of women than the overall population of HEI students and staff in Ukraine (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Percentage of women across the years within the sample and official Ukrainian HEI statistics.

3.4. Ethical Considerations

Participants were informed about the context and purpose of the study. They were also made aware that participation was voluntary, that no personal data would be collected (and anonymity therefore ensured) and that the study data would be made openly accessible. Before continuing with the survey questions, respondents then gave their consent to participate. Ethical approval for this study was waived by the Ethics Committee of the Lviv Polytechnic National University Academic Board due to the non-sensitive nature of the obtained data.

3.5. Analysis

All analysis was conducted using the software R version 4.3.3 (R Core Team, 2024). Data processing was mostly done utilising functions included in the library *tidyverse* (Wickham et al., 2019). Figures were created with *ggplot2* (Wickham, 2016) and *ggchicklet* (Rudis, 2019/2024). To ensure reproducibility, the *targets* packages was utilised (Landau, 2021) and code and data shared publicly (Kormann et al., 2024).

All data sets were translated from Ukrainian to English by two of the authors (O.B. and P.Zh.). For pre-processing of the survey data, location and type of institution were added as variables to the institutional surveys, all datasets were combined and total response time was calculated. For some analyses, the different student groups were combined into one. For analysis and presentation of results, items were rearranged into the topical groups of Open Science, reporting and academic integrity, education, and institution/administration (see Table A. 1).

For inferential analyses and group comparisons, item responses were dichotomized. Agreement items were recoded into “agree” (strongly agree, rather agree) and “disagree” (rather disagree, strongly disagree). Frequency items were recoded into “often” (very often, frequently) and “not often” (sometimes, rarely, never). Logistic regressions were performed for all statements to investigate whether the years 2022 and

2023 differed significantly in comparison to 2021 as a baseline. Therefore, these comparisons between the years were converted to dummy variables and entered into the model as predictors. McFadden's R was computed as an effect size (McFadden, 1974). To account for multiple testing, the significance threshold was Bonferroni-corrected to $\alpha = .0013$ (.05/38 as the number of statements to model).

Missing data was quite rare, since the majority of questions had to be answered in order to complete the survey. However, all content questions could be responded to with "don't know". These responses were examined separately (see section 4.2) and excluded before investigating the proportions of the other response categories. No values were imputed. No weighting or matching were applied. Since it could not be checked whether participants responded more than once across years, individuals might be included multiple times in the analysis without accounting for repeated measurement.

4. Results

4.1. Demographic Characteristics

In total, N = 24,705 respondents completed the survey across all years (only complete responses were recorded). Most participants were recruited through the national survey and in the years 2021 and 2022, with decreasing numbers in 2023 (see Table 2).

Table 2. Number of respondents per survey and year.

	2021	2022	2023	Total
National	7,987	7,727	4,560	20,274
LPU	754	1,349	530	2,633
SumDU	257	306	327	890
DonNU	125	225	231	581
LutskNTU	80	101	146	327
Total	9,203	9,708	5,794	24,705

Since the design and survey instrument do not allow reconstruction of how many individuals were reached through the various channels of recruitment, a response rate cannot be estimated.

The majority of respondents were women, with 66.2% in 2021, 61.9% in 2022, and 64.4% in 2023. All students combined (1st year up to ScD - higher doctorate - level) made up the largest group within the sample, followed by faculty, with research staff, university administrators and librarians making up only a small percentage of respondents (see also Table B. 2). Respondents without any degree also make up the largest group within the sample, with 40.5% reporting to still be studying in 2021, 52.5% in 2022 and 32.9% in 2023 (see also Table B. 3). While 61.1% of respondents in 2021, 46.8% in 2022, and 65.6% in 2023 had already published at least one research output in the last three years leading up to the survey (see also Table B. 4), fewer had experience in peer review. Of all respondents, 62.1% reported in 2021 to not have participated in any peer review in the last three years, 71.4% in 2022, and 59.9% in 2023 (see also Table B. 5 and Table B. 6 on work experience). In terms of the type of institutions, the largest groups within the sample came from technical universities, followed by classical, pedagogical, and military and internal security universities (see also Table B. 7). Education/pedagogy, law, social and behavioural sciences, information technology, humanities and health care were most represented in terms of field and discipline (see Table B. 8).

The 2022 survey contained additional questions about the respondents' and their respective HEIs' status regarding the Russian invasion of Ukraine. Of all respondents, 24.7% reported having been an internally displaced person, 12.8% reported having been a refugee abroad. Regarding whereabouts at the time of the 2022 survey, 7.1% reported to be abroad as a refugee, 12.3% to be internally displaced, 1.9% to be at home on occupied territory. Of all respondents replying to the question about their HEI's status (which was only included in the national survey), 20.2% reported that their HEI was in the area of hostilities, but territory that was now controlled by Ukraine, while 4.8% reported it to still be on occupied territory. HEIs were reported

as displaced since 2022 by 10.9% of all respondents replying to the respective question, 1.5% reported that their HEI had been displaced since 2014 (see Table B. 9 to Table B. 13).

4.2. Investigation of “*don’t know*” Responses

Across the survey, a prominent feature of the respondents’ answers is a high rate of “don’t know” answers. Across the three years, the average rate of “don’t know” responses is 19.8%. This rate differs substantially between groups of items, and also within the topical item groups (Figure 3A). There is also a general trend of items inquiring about frequency of certain practices at the HEI to receive more “don’t know” responses compared to those asking about agreement with certain statements. Of the entire sample, 33.9% on average responded “don’t know” the former, while for the latter only on average 11.6% chose this answer option.

For questions on OS the rate of “don’t know” answers lies below the overall average, but three of the ten items have rates above the group and overall average. These are the statements on publication of manuscripts in repositories, annotating datasets with appropriate metadata and the publication of source code. For reporting and academic integrity, most “don’t know” answers were obtained for the six items on occurrence of certain practices, with rates more than ten percentage points above average. Other items in this category on agreement with author rights and responsibilities were responded to with “don’t know” substantially less frequently. This aligns with the general trend of more “don’t know” responses for frequency compared to agreement questions. Statements referring to the educational context had below average rates of “don’t know” responses, with the exception of one item on the use of unauthorised software. Out of the questions regarding the institution and administration, the item on how clear processes are at the respondent’s institution (the only agreement question in this group) received overall the least “don’t know” responses, while items on the handling of misconduct had above average rates. The statement on the punishment of whistleblowers received the most “don’t know” answers out of all items with more than half of respondents choosing this option.

Figure 3B displays the change in the rate of “don’t know” answers, comparing 2022 with 2021, and likewise, 2023 with 2021, across the whole sample. The first clear trend is that the rate of “don’t know” responses unequivocally increased in 2022, but decreased in 2023, compared to 2021. The rate of change is substantial, with decreases in 2023 of up to 8 percentage points. To investigate potential differences between relevant groups within our sample, we compared developments within early-stage students without any degree with those that had at least a bachelor’s degree (see Figure C. 1 and Figure C. 2). We found the rates of “don’t know” responses among the respondents without a degree to change much more drastically, with decreases in 2023 of up to 12 percentage points. However, the overall finding of an increase in “don’t know” responses in 2022, and a decrease in 2023, both compared to 2021, remains the same across these groups.

Figure 2. Extent and development of “don’t know” answers. (A): Overall share of “don’t know” answers. The solid line represents the average across the sample, whereas the dotted line represents the average within each item group. (B): Percentage point difference of “don’t know” answers compared to 2021.

4.3. Open Science

4.3.1. Overview

There were ten items within the survey to investigate the extent to which respondents agree with certain statements on OS. We first analysed respondents' agreement across the different items by comparing responses across the entire sample from 2021 to 2023 after exclusion of "don't know" and missing responses (see Figure 3).

As a general trend we observed that the majority of respondents agreed with the statements on OS (except for one), indicating that OS practices are generally perceived as relevant and desirable. Highest agreement was found on the statement that research results should be openly accessible. On this item, 92.5% of respondents agreed, with more than half agreeing strongly. This was followed by a large share (87.9%) of respondents agreeing that they understand the concept of OS. The statement that research papers should be openly accessible before peer review received least agreement, with only 38.4% of respondents agreeing. This marks a substantial drop from the second-least agreed upon statement on the publication of source code with 65.3% agreement. Statements on different aspects of OPR differed slightly, with highest agreement on open identities, followed by direct communication between authors and reviewers, and least agreement on the publication of peer review reports.

The most agreed upon statement on OA also received the least "don't know" and missing responses, but was followed in this by the least agreed upon statements. Most "don't know" and missing answers were recorded for the items on publication of source code followed by the publication of author manuscripts in open online repositories, the second and fourth statement with the least agreement, respectively.

Figure 3. Distribution of responses on agreement with statements about OS for the entire sample from 2021 to 2023.

4.3.2. Development over Time

To investigate developments over time, response categories were plotted across the three annual surveys for all items on OS (see Figure 4). We observed no strong general trends of changes across years. One development that we found persistently across seven out of ten items was an increase in strong agreement between 2021 and 2023, while weak agreement decreased for six out of these seven statements. Strong agreement remained stable for OA and the description of experimental data with appropriate metadata, and decreased for open identities of peer reviewers. Rates of strong and weak disagreement did not develop greatly between 2021 and 2023, except for one item that stands out. Descriptively, the most substantial development was found for the statement on providing access to research results prior to peer review. In 2021, 36.9% of respondents agreed, while 44.9% agreed in 2023.

In logistic regressions, we identified significantly higher agreement in 2022 compared to 2021 for the items on appropriate metadata, all three OPR items, and the understanding of the concept of OS. However, statements on metadata and OPR did not differ significantly anymore between 2023 and 2021. For the year 2023, higher agreement compared to 2021 could be identified for statements about OA, access prior to peer review, and understanding of OS. Descriptive differences were quite small, effect sizes were minimal and no other comparison reached significance (see Table C. 1 percentages, statistics, and effect sizes).

Figure 4. Proportion of responses for each answer category for agreement with statements on OS (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

4.3.3. Comparison by Academic Role

Differences between the responses of different members of the academic community were also investigated (see Figure 5). Students across years and levels (1st year to ScD level) were combined for the purpose of this analysis (see Figure C. 3 for detailed differences between student subgroups).

As a general trend it can be observed that librarians (the smallest among the compared groups) tend to agree more than other groups with the statements on OS. We observed the greatest consensus on the statement about OA publishing. Rates of agreement ranged very minimally from 90.8% among students in 2021 to 97.7% in librarians in 2023. The different groups also reported quite consistently on open data, with agreement rates ranging from 81.5% among students in 2021 to 94.4% among librarians in 2023. All groups reported similar levels of understanding of the concept of OS, with the exception of students. While the rate of agreement on this item ranged between 91.0% for university administrators and 97.4% for librarians in 2023, only 83.6% of students agreed that year. Regarding the statement about making papers available before peer review, the different groups also responded quite similarly with librarians appearing most favourable, while research staff agreed rarely.

We observed the largest group differences on the responses to statements regarding OPR. Opinions especially diverged in 2023. That year, 88.9% of students agreed with making peer reviewer identities public, compared to only 56.0% of research staff. Open peer review reports were favoured by 87.2% of librarians, but only 52.8% of research staff. We observed the largest discrepancy between responses on the statement about direct communication between authors and peer reviewers. While students agreed most at 88.7%, less than half of research staff agreed with 43.4%. This statement also saw the most pronounced decrease in agreement across years in any group, with initially 67.0% of research staff agreeing in 2021. Research staff decreasingly agreed with open peer reviewer identities, as well. OPR is seen most favourably by students and librarians, while faculty and university administrators agree less and research staff approve of this OS practice least. We observed the largest increases in agreement over time within groups for students and research staff on publishing reports before peer review, where agreement respectively rose more than 9 percentage points from 2021 to 2023.

Figure 5. Extent of agreement with statements on OS by academic role/group (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

4.4. Reporting and Academic Integrity

4.4.1. Overview

On reporting and academic integrity participants responded to nine questions on their agreement. Topics revolved around authorship, researchers' rights and responsibilities. One of these items, namely "Changes to experimental data after the end of the experiment are acceptable" is the only statement phrased contrary to the others. Another six items inquired about the frequency of certain QRPs at the respondents' HEIs that violate principles of research integrity. We first compared responses across agreement items (see Figure 6) and frequency items (see Figure 7) across the entire sample.

Agreement with statements on responsible reporting practices and academic integrity was generally very high. All statements had more than 80% agreement among respondents, except for one item on changes to experimental data. Respondents agreed most with the statement on indicating authorship for all contributors (96.4%), followed by full responsibility of all co-authors (91.3%). Apart from the inverted item on experimental data, participants were least in favour of describing all details of research to ensure reproducibility (80.1%) and publishing both positive and negative results (82.6%). However, agreement on these statements follows the overall trend of very high rates. Within this group of items, the statement "Changes to experimental data after the end of the experiment are acceptable" is an exception not only in phrasing, but also in the rates of agreement observed. We found that 38.5% disagree, indicating that only a minority disapproves of this practice. Questions on intellectual property rights and describing details to ensure reproducibility had in sum most "don't know" and missing responses.

For all practices, between 8.4% and 18.8% reported that they occur very often or frequently. Up to 46.4% reported that they occur at least sometimes. Selective citations were reported as most common, with 18.8% reporting that as very often or frequently, this is followed by using own previous publications without proper acknowledgement with 16.5%. Passing off other people's achievement as one's own was reported as least common, however, with 8.4% of respondents stating that it occurs at least frequently, followed by fabrication of data and facts by 9.3%. The relative scarcity as a percentage of the whole should not diminish from the fact that these levels are quite worrying when considering the seriousness of the violations of integrity, a point we pick up in the discussion. We found intermediate frequencies for practices related to ghostwriting and plagiarism. Rates of "don't know" responses were quite similar across all practices and generally very high. Questions on the frequency of practices received substantially more "don't know" responses than questions on the agreement with statements.

Figure 6. Distribution of responses on agreement with statements about reporting and academic integrity for the entire sample from 2021 to 2023.

Figure 7. Distribution of responses on the frequency of certain questionable practices related to reporting and academic integrity at the respondents' respective HEIs for the entire sample from 2021 to 2023.

4.4.2. Development over Time

In general, response categories for the agreement with statements were distributed quite similarly across the years (see Figure 8). For almost all statements, strong agreement increased slightly, while weak agreement decreased. The only exception to this trend is the statement on indicating authorship of all contributors. There, strong agreement decreases over the years, while weak agreement increases slightly. Disagreement was already quite low in 2021 and remained relatively stable throughout the years. We observed the most pronounced change in the item on changes to experimental data (which was phrased opposite to all other statements). Strong agreement with this statement increased with a lesser decrease in weak agreement. Disagreement decreased overall, meaning over the years, more respondents reported to find the practice acceptable.

We also confirmed this observation in our inferential analysis, performing logistic regressions. Agreement with the statement on changes to experimental data was more likely in 2022 compared to 2021 (61.5% vs. 58.8% respondents agreeing), as well as in 2023 compared to 2021 (65.5% vs. 58.8%). We found the only other significant difference (after Bonferroni-correction) for the reporting of conflicts of interest, with 90.2% agreeing in 2023 compared to 87.8% in 2021. However, the descriptive difference between years in this item is comparably small with less than half of the difference in the item on changes to experimental data. Effect sizes were minimal, and no other comparison reached significance (see

Table C. 2 for percentages, statistics, and effect sizes).

The reported frequency of questionable practices at the HEIs was lower in 2022 compared to 2021 (see Figure 9). However, we found this trend to reverse for the year 2023. All practices were reported as more frequent in 2023 compared to 2021, with increases of “very often” and “frequently” responses ranging between 2.0% and 4.2%. We observed very similar trends on items on claiming authorship to work that was arranged for others to perform, fabricating data or facts, and passing off other people’s achievements as one’s own. For these practices, “never” and “rarely” responses decreased, while all other categories were chosen more often. Changes in response categories differed for the other three practices. There, respondents reported practices to occur “never” more often in 2023 compared to 2021, while “rarely” responses decreased. We identified the largest increase in frequency for fabricating data or facts and passing off other people’s achievements as one’s own.

In our inferential analysis performing logistic regressions, we found that comparing 2022 to 2021 did not predict any significant change in reported frequency (although all numbers dropped). However, respondents were significantly more likely to respond “very often” or “frequently” in 2023 compared to 2021 for all practices but one, namely using another author’s work without proper reference. Only using year as predictors achieved only very minor effect sizes (see Table C. 3 for percentages, statistics, and effect sizes).

Figure 8. Proportion of responses for each answer category for agreement with statements on reporting and academic integrity (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure 9. Proportion of responses for each answer category on how frequently certain practices occur at the respondent’s HEI related to reporting and academic integrity (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

4.4.3. Comparison by Academic Role

We first investigated group differences for the agreement with statements on authorship, researcher’s rights and responsibilities (see Figure 10). Students of different levels were combined into one group for this comparison (see Figure C. 6 for detailed figures on student subgroups). As with statements on OS, librarians tend to agree most. We observed generally good consensus among groups, with most similar levels of agreement in 2022 and more divergence in responses in 2021 and 2023.

Regarding reporting conflicts of interest, students deviated most by agreeing substantially less, especially in 2022 (83.5% of students agreeing vs. 92.8% of faculty). Librarians agreed more with describing research in detail to ensure methodology, with 94.0% agreeing in 2023, e.g., compared to 83.3% of students. For the inverted statement on changes to experimental data, there is a pronounced split between the groups, with students and librarians agreeing quite often compared to administrators, research staff, and faculty. In 2023, 74.7% of librarians found changes to experimental data acceptable compared to 51.4% of faculty. Changes within groups over the years were not as pronounced as in some of the OS items. Within students the acceptance of changes to experimental data increased more than 9 percentage points from 2021 to 2023. Over 7 percentage points more research staff agreed with describing research in detail to ensure reproducibility in 2023 compared to 2021. Administrators agreed less with the statement on the broad public purpose of research, with more than 7 percentage points less agreement in 2023.

When examining group differences in reported frequency of certain practices at HEIs, we found it difficult to establish any general trends across items (see Figure 11). Reporting differed most for the occurrence of selective citations with 26.1% of research staff estimating it to be frequent in 2023 compared to 12.8% of administrators. Using another author’s work without proper referencing was also perceived quite differently depending on the group. In 2023, 10.8% of students reported it to happen often compared to 6.9% of administrators. We observed the most pronounced changes from 2021 to 2023 in reporting in research staff which had an increase of more than 14 and more than 10 percentage points in reporting frequent selective citations and use of own previous publications without proper referencing, respectively. Librarians reporting selective citations to be frequent increased by more than 8 percentage points. We found the biggest decrease in university administrators, where over 7 percentage points less respondents reported that authors use other work without proper reference in 2023 compared to 2021.

Figure 10. Extent of agreement with statements on reporting and academic integrity by academic role/group (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure 11. Rates of questionable practices to occur often at the respondent’s HEI by academic role/group (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

4.5. Education

4.5.1. Overview

The survey included seven items about educational aspects, four of determining agreement to statements, with the remaining three probing the frequency of certain practices. We first analysed respondents’ agreement across the different items by comparing responses across the entire sample from 2021 to 2023 after exclusion of “don’t know” and missing responses (see Figure 12).

Most respondents agreed with the statements on education, with at least 75% of respondents agreeing or strongly agreeing to each of the four items (Figure 13). 94.3% of respondents agreed with the statement that students should understand what constitutes inappropriate academic behaviour and report it to the appropriate authorities. For all four items, the rate of “don’t know” responses was below sample average, and below 15% overall. Asked about the frequency of students engaging in academic misconduct, 11.8% of respondents reported students helping each other during exams or tests very often, 21.8% frequently, and 31.5% sometimes. Students were reported to less frequently use unauthorised/pirated software, with 46.9% of respondents answering “never”, and 13.7% answering “rarely”. However, the rate of “don’t know” responses for this item was high, with more than 30% of respondents answering that way.

Figure 12. Distribution of responses on agreement with statements about education for the entire sample from 2021 to 2023.

Figure 13. Distribution of responses on the frequency of certain questionable practices related to education at the respondents' respective HEIs for the entire sample from 2021 to 2023.

4.5.2. Development over Time

Across the seven items on education, only weak temporal trends are observable (Figure 14). Similar to our findings on previous topics (see sections 4.3.2 and 4.4.2), the share of “strongly agree” responses increased from 2021 to 2023, partly coupled with a decrease in “rather agree” responses (“Students must understand what constitutes inappropriate academic behavior”, and “The quality of educational services at my higher education institution is high”), or a decrease in “rather disagree” and “strongly disagree” (“Students should openly publish the full texts of their diploma theses”). In our inferential analysis we found a significant increase in general agreement for OA publication of theses and open educational resources in 2022 compared to 2021, while there was a slight decrease for the quality of higher education. However, comparing 2023 to 2021, respondents were only more likely to agree with the statement on OA publication of theses. Additionally, we only found very small effect sizes for our logistic regression models (see Table C. 4).

Figure 14. Proportion of responses for each answer category for agreement with statements on education (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Regarding the frequency of academic misconduct among students, respondents indicating the frequent use of unauthorised aids during exams and the use of pirated software both increased substantially in 2023, but not in 2022 (Figure 15). We could confirm this observation through performing logistic regressions. Comparing 2023 to 2021 showed a significant increase for the reported frequency of using unauthorised aids during exams and use of pirated software. No other comparison reached significance in our inferential analysis (see Table C. 5).

Figure 15. Proportion of responses for each answer category on how frequently certain practices occur at the respondent’s HEI related to education (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

4.5.3. Comparison by Academic Role

Comparing the educational items across academic roles, we note multiple salient findings (Figure 16). First, the variation between the academic roles differs substantially between the four agreement items on education. Whereas all groups unequivocally support the statement that students must understand what constitutes inappropriate academic behaviour (more than 90% agreement in all groups), open access to educational resources and open publishing of diploma theses elicited disparate responses between the groups with up to 29 percentage point differences in 2021 for open access to educational resources. Second, there is no clear temporal trend on any of the four items, with some groups exhibiting an increase, and others a decrease in agreement to the statements. Most notably, students exhibit lower agreement with the requirement to publish their diploma theses than all other groups, but still agreed in 65.7% to 77.5% cases. Likewise, when asked about openly sharing educational materials, faculty and university administrators agreed the least (64.5% to 71.9%), with librarians and students exhibiting much higher agreement (close to or above 90%).

Figure 16. Extent of agreement with statements on education by academic role/group (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Considering the three items on the frequency of academic misconduct, we observe a general increase in the share of respondents answering “very often” or “frequently”. In particular, we observe a substantive increase in the proportion of research staff members reporting frequent academic misconduct among students (Figure 17).

Figure 17. Rates of practices to occur often in education at the respondent’s HEI by academic role/group (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

4.6. Institution/Administration

4.6.1. Overview

The survey included five items on the frequency of questionable practices by institutions/administration and one general item on how transparent processes are at the respondent's HEI. Overall, respondents rated questionable practices by their institution/administration to "frequently" or "very often" take place in 6.2% to 21.0% across the five items (Figure 18). The item with the highest reported frequency concerns university administrations accusing and punishing whistleblowers of academic integrity violations, with 21.0% responding "very often" or "frequently", and 18.0% responding with "sometimes". All other items are reported to be substantially less frequent, with 6.2% respondents indicating incitements of violations of academic integrity at their institution as occurring "very often" or "frequently". A large majority of respondents (89.7%) agreed that processes at their HEI were organised clearly and transparently (Figure 19).

However, all five frequency items exhibit rates of "don't know" responses which are substantially above average (see also section 4.2). For each of the items, at least 30% of respondent's answered "don't know", with 51.6% "don't know" responses for the item with highest reported frequency ("accusation and punishment of whistleblowers"). The question on how processes are organised at the respondent's HEI received least "don't know" responses of all items (1.9%).

Figure 18. Distribution of responses on the frequency of certain institutional/administrative practices at the respondents' respective HEIs for the entire sample from 2021 to 2023.

Figure 19. Distribution of responses on agreement with processes being clear and transparent at the respondent's HEI for the entire sample from 2021 to 2023.

4.6.2. Development over Time

All practices were reported more often as occurring “very often” or “frequently” in the year 2023, after only slight changes from 2021 to 2022 (Figure 20). We found the largest increase in respondents reporting a practice as occurring often for abuse of position to encourage dishonesty, followed by incitement to violate academic integrity and false accusations of violations (all increasing by more than 4 percentage points in sum). Agreement with the statement on transparent and clear processes at the respondent’s HEI saw a slight decrease in 2022, returning to baseline in 2023, however with more strong and less weak agreement (Figure 21).

These trends were all confirmed within the inferential analysis. We found the degree to which practices are reported as happening often to be significantly higher in 2023 compared to 2021. Significantly less respondents agreed with processes at their HEI to be organised clearly and transparently in 2022 compared to 2021, but this difference disappeared again in 2023 (see Table C. 6 and Table C. 7 for models and effect sizes).

Figure 20. Proportion of responses for each answer category on how frequently certain institutional/administrative practices occur at the respondent’s HEI related (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure 21. Proportion of responses for each answer category for agreement with processes being clear and transparent at the respondent’s HEI (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

4.6.3. Comparison by Academic Role

When comparing responses regarding institutional and administrative practices, administrators tend to report practices as least common, while students and research staff report them as happening more often (Figure 22). This trend is consistent for all items, but the punishment of whistleblowers, which is reported more often by administrators compared to, e.g., research staff. Punishment of whistleblowers is also the practice where responses differ most between groups, with 27.4% of students reporting it as often in 2023 compared to 9.4% of librarians. This is followed by reports on tolerating and encouraging dishonesty, while reports on the latter mostly diverge in 2023 (17.8% among research staff report as often compared to 4.6% of university administrators). We observed the largest changes in responses between 2021 and 2023 within research staff and librarians. Both reported punishment for whistleblowers as less frequent (more than 10 percentage point reduction for librarians, more than 7 for research staff). Over 10 percentage points more of research staff reported abuse of official position to occur often, and over 7 percentage points more reported that misconduct was tolerated frequently or very often. More librarians reported incitement to violate academic integrity to occur often, with a more than 7 percentage point increase.

Regarding agreement with the statement on institutional processes, university administrators agree most that these are organised well (96.1% in 2023) compared to 85.8% of research staff in 2023 (Figure 23). However, levels of agreement do not differ greatly across groups.

Figure 22. Rates of institutional/administrative practices to occur often at the respondent’s HEI by academic role/group (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure 23. Extent of agreement with statement on processes being clear and transparent at the respondent’s HEI by academic role/group (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

5. Discussion

The survey results provide insight into the evolving awareness, attitudes, and behaviours regarding Open Science (OS) and academic integrity among students, researchers, and staff at Ukrainian higher education institutions (HEIs) over three years (2021-2023). Interpretation of the results requires care due to three factors: (1) the survey was iteratively collected over a relatively short period of time, (2) impacts of the global COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine are somewhat unknown variables, (3) methodological issues with survey distribution mean that the extent to which the samples are comparable year-to-year is ambiguous.

Furthermore, comparing this data to previous findings from the literature poses certain challenges, since these studies differ in samples, contexts, and especially the specific phrasing of items. However, this survey provides a good benchmark to monitor future developments within Ukrainian HEIs on awareness, attitudes, and behaviours regarding Open Science (OS) and academic integrity. Below we discuss the results on the individual aspects in detail and relate them to the existing literature where possible.

5.1. Awareness and Knowledge

All survey items gave participants the option to respond with “don’t know”. The literature on survey research discusses multiple potential reasons for such answers (Young, 2012): a style of generally answering “don’t know”, a desire to give a satisfactory answer where providing truthful answers might be too cumbersome (satisficing), respondents refusing to answer, potentially due to their response being socially uncomfortable or sensitive, and finally, as valid responses due to a lack of attitude or opinion on the topic under consideration. Respondents chose “don’t know” as an answer quite frequently in the survey, with substantial variation between items and rates of up to 51.6% of “don’t know” responses for the item on punishment of whistleblowers. We conducted multiple analyses to ascertain potential reasons for the high rates of “don’t know” responses. We found no substantive relationship between the response time and the number of “don’t know” answers. We further found only weak differences between academic roles and the number of “don’t know”s, with first year students and librarians exhibiting higher rates of “don’t know”s. Taken together, these findings suggest that a substantive interpretation of “don’t know” responses is warranted: there are no obvious third variables that explain them, and respondents who are likely to possess lower knowledge of the Open Science and research integrity (1st year students) have higher rates of “don’t know” responses. We therefore interpret these responses as a lack of awareness or knowledge of the subject matter. This assumed lack of knowledge or awareness likely stems from some respondents not having had interactions with the topic of OS or the included aspects of academic integrity. In addition, respondents might have found it easier to report their personal attitudes than to estimate other people’s behaviours, which would explain that respective items received substantially more “don’t know” responses.

Some questions might not have been relevant to all participants. For example, students in their first years of study might not have had interactions with publishing and respective ethical questions, and might therefore not (yet) have had an opinion on related statements. Our sample consists of a large share of students and individuals without publishing or academic work experience. Previous findings suggest, for instance, that awareness on OS topics increases with career seniority in early-career researchers (Berezko, Medina, et al., 2021). We observed the highest level of “don’t know” responses in 2022, the year where the share of students is highest within our sample. Differences in the composition of the sample and lack of awareness among students could therefore potentially explain the changing rates between years. However, when investigating respondents with and without a degree separately, we found a similar trend of an increase in

“don’t know” responses in 2022 and a decrease in 2023. Potentially, the survey reached a broader and generally less aware population in 2022, that might not have responded as much in other years. The situation in Ukraine might also have influenced response behaviour in 2022. With the pandemic and the war disrupting regular academic processes, estimating how often certain practices occur might have been complicated by more distance learning, less direct contact and less opportunity to monitor academic integrity.

For reporting and academic integrity, “don’t know” responses were most prevalent for questions on the occurrence of questionable practices regarding citations, referencing and plagiarism, possibly reflecting difficulties in distinguishing acceptable from unacceptable practices. This suggests low confidence in understanding the nuances of academic integrity, which could stem from insufficient education or inconsistent enforcement of policies. Low publication experience within the sample, as indicated by demographic data, further supports this interpretation. These findings are consistent with Childers and Bruton (2016), who found similar uncertainty among students regarding complex citation issues. Additionally, certain practices might only occur very rarely or go often undetected, limiting student’s exposure to existing norms around them.

Regarding the educational context, respondents chose “don’t know” considerably more often on the question about the use of unauthorised or “pirated” software compared to others. We speculate that unauthorised software might be a less familiar concept to the respondents or might apply more to some fields than others.

Respondents seem most unsure on questions about how misconduct is treated at their HEI. These questions might inquire about rather rare incidences or practices that are not very noticeable to all members of an institution. Respondents might also feel more pressure to avoid socially unacceptable responses, thus opting for “don’t know” absent better knowledge of established norms and practices.

We interpret the decrease in “don’t know” responses in 2023, compared to 2022 and 2021 as an increase in awareness, knowledge, or the confidence to respond to certain questions. While we cannot rule out that this might be caused by differences in sampling, increased awareness might be attributed to the introduction of the National Open Science Plan and the efforts of government and non-governmental initiatives.

5.2. Attitudes and Behaviours

5.2.1. Open Science

Within our survey respondents we found a quite good understanding of OS. Including missing and “don’t know” responses, over 70% of the entire sample agreed that they felt they could explain the concept of OS. Our sample included a quite large share of students, who reported better understanding of OS the more advanced they were in their studies, indicating that they become more familiar with the concept over the course of their higher education.

Attitudes towards OS practices were generally positive, with majority agreement on almost all statements. OS appears to be desirable for members of Ukrainian HEIs, similar to previous investigations among researchers who reported more hopes than fears related to it (Abele-Brehm et al., 2019). OA publishing was viewed most favourably, followed by Open Data, consistent with previous similar studies (Digital Science et al., 2023; Harpe, 2024; Ross-Hellauer et al., 2017). In Ukraine, OA publishing is - through legislation, culture and infrastructure - a well-established practice (Kaliuzhna & Hauschke, 2024), while Open/FAIR Data is one

main focus of the recently introduced National Open Science Plan (Government of Ukraine, 2022). The existing policy focus, combined with high agreement towards OS by the survey respondents, indicates that OS practices are on their way to becoming mainstream, with OA already being a more common practice.

While different groups within the academic community appear to view many OS practices in similar ways, their opinions diverged most for OPR. Overall, respondents agreed more with open identities (82.3%), compared to open interaction (77.3%) and open reports (73.7%). This stands in contrast to the survey by Ross-Hellauer et al. (2017), who report finding much lower agreement. In addition, the ranking of the agreement to the three items (from open identities to open reports) was opposite in the survey by Ross-Hellauer et al., with higher support for open interaction (68% in favour) and open reports (59%) than for open identities (31% in favour). The differences between the two studies might be explained by our survey including many students which we found to hold more positive opinions on OS practices than researchers, while the study by Ross-Hellauer et al. did not target students at all, but only active authors, editors and reviewers. In our survey, those involved most in peer review (i.e., research staff) generally were least open to implementing OPR practices and even reported a less positive attitude in 2023 compared to the years before. This finding bears special relevance for the OPTIMA project, since it aims to introduce OPR practices to the academic community in Ukraine through a dedicated platform. Based on our findings we would expect more difficulties establishing OPR practices with experienced academics. The attitudes of this cohort are of particular value, however, since they are the group most likely to have experience with peer review systems. Hence, as students, for example, are introduced to such systems, we may expect their levels of enthusiasm to diminish.

Making research publications openly available before peer review (i.e., preprinting, although this term was not specifically used within the survey) seemed to be the most controversial among our survey respondents, with 38.4% of survey respondents agreeing. However, agreement increased noticeably between 2021 and 2023. Previous studies of attitudes towards preprints have mixed findings, but generally tend to find positive attitudes towards preprints. Soderberg et al. (2020) report 69.73% of respondents to be favourable towards preprints. Ni and Waltman (Ni & Waltman, 2024) report on respondent's willingness to post preprints in the future, which is not directly comparable to general attitudes. Nevertheless, they report large shares of respondents (above 50% for most fields and countries) to be willing to post some of their papers as preprints in the future. Reporting on a survey among pharmacy researchers, Harpe (2024) reports a generally positive attitude towards preprinting. He further reports respondents holding considerably more positive opinions about other OS practices, such as sharing of materials, data, or code, which is in line with our results. Finally, the item on preprints enclosed in our survey was phrased in a potentially suggestive way ("Research papers should be openly available even before the official peer review process, i.e. before a thorough review of their content." [emphasis ours]), which might have itself led to lower approval.

In general, students and the academic community at Ukrainian HEIs are quite open to a variety of OS practices. Their attitudes remained stable on this high level over the three years of this survey, with only minimal changes. Improvement of attitudes towards some practices is still possible and the aim of several initiatives, however, we might only see more downstream effects over a longer time period. This survey, however, cannot give details about the actual behaviours regarding OS. It is very likely that although a high number of respondents agreed with the OS statements, only a smaller part of the sample actually engages in these practices.

5.2.2. Reporting and Academic Integrity

The statements referring to research and academic integrity mainly relate to issues around rights and responsibilities of authors when reporting their research. Since students also take part in research activities, they are also affected by the principles discussed in this section of the survey. Agreement with these statements (except for one) was generally very high across different groups within academia and also over the years. Levels of agreement remained quite stable over time, with a slight trend towards strong instead of weak agreement. We observed that almost all respondents are of the opinion that authorship of all contributors needs to be indicated. Fewer people agreed that all details of research should be described in detail to achieve reproducibility. However, since this statement also received the most “don’t know” responses, respondents might have been unclear on what this entails and aims at.

The survey included one item which was phrased in reverse. The statement “*Changes to experimental data after the end of the experiment are acceptable*” refers to a questionable instead of responsible practice. A majority of respondents still agreed with this statement. This is a concerning result if assumed to be true, especially in the light of 43.5% reporting that fabrication occurs at their HEI. However, it might be unlikely that this would be the only principle of academic integrity the respondents do not think should be followed. We must be careful in interpreting this result, since people might have had a tendency to agree and could have missed this single reversed phrasing. Also, while groups have high consensus across other items, responses diverge most here. The higher agreement of students and librarians to this item might imply that they are less opposed to making changes to experimental data. However, due to a potential lack of familiarity with the practices mentioned they might also have had a more general tendency to agree or a higher risk of missing the inverted phrasing.

When asked about the prevalence of QRPs around reporting at their HEI, most respondents reported them as not occurring often. Less than half of the sample reported that these practices occur at least sometimes at their institution. It is difficult, however, to compare these results with numbers on individual behaviours from previous studies due to the difference in observational units (occurrence at institution, department, or individual behaviour). We would expect numbers reported on entire institutions to be higher than numbers from reports on one’s own behaviour for two reasons: first, one instance can be reported by several people independently, leading to higher total counts. Second, respondents might feel lower pressure to answer in a socially desirable way when reporting on their colleagues’ behaviour compared to their own.

Fabrication and plagiarism were reported as happening least often. This is in line with previous findings that these severe violations are less prevalent than other QRPs (Fanelli, 2009; Gopalakrishna, Riet, et al., 2022; Pupovac & Fanelli, 2015; Xie et al., 2021). The levels identified in this survey are raising concerns by being notably higher compared to other studies that estimate approximately 2% to 4% of researchers to have been involved in such practices. In the current study, the questions were phrased to inquire about occurrence at entire HEIs instead of individual behaviour. Xie et al. report that 15.5% of researchers have witnessed severe misconduct by others at least once. While not clear whether reports in the current study are shaped by first-hand experiences, rumours or other estimates, 38.8% and 43.5% report plagiarism and fabrication, respectively, to occur at their HEI (at least rarely). These levels are quite alarming when considering the seriousness of these academic integrity violations and their implications for the validity of research results. Respondents reported observing QRPs around citations as more minor violations more frequently than those on fabrication and plagiarism. One possible explanation is that since students tend to have difficulty assessing

more complex issues around citations (Childers & Bruton, 2016), they might engage in QRPs without being fully aware of them.

Investigating trends over time, we made the slightly concerning observation, that reported frequencies are higher in 2023 than in 2021. However, we cannot determine whether this represents a change in actual behaviours or potentially increased awareness or monitoring of QRPs. In general, university administrators tend to report QRPs as happening less frequently compared to research staff and students. The latter two groups might have more insight into their own and their peers' behaviour, while administrators might report more positively about their institutions.

5.2.3. Education

We investigated all questions jointly that referred specifically to the educational context. One general question on the high quality of educational services at the respondent's HEI received high agreement (87.7%), with slightly less than half of the sample strongly agreeing. Agreement decreased slightly for 2022, potentially because of the educational system being especially burdened by the war. Interestingly, university administrators (and to some extent faculty), bearing more responsibility for the quality of the education, rated the quality higher than students, who are the ones affected by it, demonstrating differences in perspective.

Among the items on education, respondents agreed most with the statement that students should *"understand what constitutes inappropriate academic behavior and report it to the appropriate authorities"*. However, there are some barriers in implementing this in practice. On the one hand, previous studies suggest that students are often not aware of which behaviours are acceptable and which are not (Childers & Bruton, 2016; Liut et al., 2024). On the other hand, students' willingness to report academic misconduct to authorities likely depends on prior experience with the outcomes of such reports. As the responses to other questions in this survey suggest (see section below), reports on misconduct might not always be met with the desired reactions by the authorities.

Providing open access to educational resources was agreed with slightly less, but still by 79.8%. This refers to the concept of Open Educational Resources (OERs), which is interrelated with the concept of OS and refers to openly providing educational materials for the public to use non-commercially (Havemann, 2016). For instance, the OPTIMA project aims to create such resources on topics of OS. Even though the relevance of such resources likely increases with higher relevance of digital information technology in education, e.g., because of more need for distance learning, we did not find more agreement in 2023 compared to the previous years. Faculty and university administrators seem especially sceptical about this practice. This is noteworthy, since these groups bear the burden of providing such resources, while students are the ones benefiting from or depending on them.

Compared to the OA publishing of research results, respondents agree noticeably less with OA publishing of diploma theses by students (75.2% agreement). While students' attitudes towards OA publishing of research results are similar to those of other groups, they are least likely to agree to their theses being published OA. This discrepancy might come from expectations of increased effort and potential negative consequences of their work being out in the open. However, students would also potentially benefit most from being able to access theses written by their colleagues.

Helping each other during tests or exams is reported as the most common among the dishonest practices referring to studying specifically (65.1% sometimes or more often), followed by using unauthorised aids during exams (48.5% sometimes or more often). This exceeds the numbers reported in a previous Ukrainian survey, which, however, only inquired about occurrence at departments, not entire HEIs (OECD, 2017). We also observed increases, especially in how often use of unauthorised aids during exams and use of pirated software were reported in 2023 compared to 2021. This apparent increase of dishonest practices could be attributed to multiple factors. Firstly, external circumstances, such as the distance learning resulting from the pandemic and displacement of some HEIs might have led to an actual increase of cheating behaviour. Secondly, there might also have been an increase in awareness around these issues, leading to behaviours being noticed more often or estimated as being more frequent.

In general, we do not see great developments in attitudes over the years of our survey, but do observe some increase related to questionable behaviours. However, we note that the perception of the status quo and the desired directions within education at Ukrainian HEIs differ depending on the role respondents take within the academic community. Notably, there seems to be a generally positive attitude to OS and OS practices across Ukrainian higher education. Yet, individual members of the community who would have to invest time and resources into OS practices (e.g., faculty and university administrators with OERs), or might be affected by them (OA publishing of student theses) seem to hold less favourable views on the respective questions.

5.2.4. Institution/Administration

On questions regarding questionable institutional/administrative practices, many participants overall responded with “don’t know”, complicating the full interpretation of the remaining answers. However, punishment of whistleblowers was reported as occurring most, with 21% reporting it to happen frequently or very often. This is a startling result, since a large majority of our sample also agrees that students should report inappropriate academic behaviour. All other questionable practices were reported as happening substantially less frequently at Ukrainian HEIs, but with an increase of all practices from 2021 to 2023. Again, it remains unclear whether this actually indicates a higher prevalence, or if some issues are noticed more often due to higher awareness. In general, research staff and students reported observing institutional misconduct most often, while university administrators reported observing it least often. Presumably, affected individuals perceive a higher prevalence compared to those bearing more responsibility. These results can serve as a benchmark for future developments and help illuminate different perspectives regarding institutional and administrative processes.

Lastly, one statement inquired about how clear and transparent respondents perceive processes at their HEI to be. A large proportion of respondents agreed with the statement “*Overall, the processes at my higher education institution are organised in a clear and transparent manner*”, with a marginal dip in 2022, potentially related to the circumstances of war. University administrators agreed most with this statement, while opinions deviated slightly for other groups, with research staff, students, and faculty tending to agree less. Administrators potentially want to portray their HEIs in the most positive light, while other groups are more critical. However, processes at Ukrainian HEIs seem to be organised well overall.

5.3. Summary

In sum, we observed overall very positive attitudes towards OS and principles of academic integrity. Over the years 2021-2023, there appears to not have been very pronounced developments, with responses only changing slightly overall. Group differences often followed similar patterns, with students and research staff, and university administrators and faculty, respectively, being more similar in their responses. Often, opinions diverged along the question of who would be more affected, or responsible for implementation. For instance, students agreed less with their theses being published OA, while research staff were least open to OPR practices, and vice versa. Reports on behaviours also differ between groups, indicating different levels of awareness or distinct reporting tendencies, e.g., with responses by university administrators painting a more positive picture.

Our findings should be interpreted in the context of the pandemic and war. The increased prevalence of distance learning due to COVID-19 may have reduced opportunities for informal learning about the practices of peers, contributing to the high “don’t know” responses observed. The war has created additional disruptions, including displacement and changes in institutional structures, which likely affect both awareness and reported behaviours. In this context, the observed differences in the frequency of academic misconduct might reflect both actual behavioural changes and increased awareness or scrutiny during challenging circumstances. For example, the rise in reported misconduct in 2023 could be due to heightened awareness or better monitoring by institutions as they adapted to ongoing challenges.

5.4. Limitations

Several limiting factors should be mentioned, including on aspects of the study design. Since respondents could participate in multiple years, the survey does not have a pure longitudinal cohort design. This creates potential overlap amongst participants across years without the ability to track intra-individual changes, making it difficult to assess true longitudinal changes. We have treated the years as independent samples in our analysis, knowing that there is some overlap, but not to which degree. Additionally, demographic differences across samples, especially the 2022 cohort, complicate direct comparisons. The 2022 sample included more students and therefore may have included more first-time respondents or individuals less familiar with OS and academic integrity issues, which may partly explain the differences in awareness levels. Channels of recruitment or motivation to participate might have differed between years. Recruitment methods for this survey were chosen to reach as many participants as possible. However, this convenience sampling approach with a multitude of recruitment channels makes response rate estimations very difficult and might limit representativeness (despite the large sample size). Compared to our target population, some groups are overrepresented in our sample, such as women, OPTIMA partner institutions, and potentially specific regions, limiting generalizability of our findings.

Additionally, the lack of clarity in phrasing for some survey items and the high number of “don’t know” responses may indicate superficial engagement with the survey content by some respondents. However, the absence of compensation or enforcement means that the likelihood of intentional misreporting was likely low. Questions on the prevalence of QRPs were phrased to refer to the entire institution, not the respondents’ individual behaviours. Estimating others’ behaviour might be more difficult than reporting on one’s own, leading to discrepancies (see also Christensen et al., 2020). Finally, our inferential analyses are explorations to gain additional insights into the patterns we identified descriptively. However, they should not be interpreted as stand-alone results or confirmatory tests.

5.5. Recommendations

The findings present implications for policy development in general and for future iterations of this survey approach to gauging development of attitudes and practices. Regarding the former, there is still room for improvement of knowledge on OS and academic integrity across all levels of academia in Ukraine, but particularly for students. In our sample, students reported being least confident in their understanding of the concept of OS, while holding very positive attitudes towards OS practices. This openness might offer great opportunities to build capacity in future researchers and teachers when combined with additional education and training. Some aspects of OS appear to be less well-known, such as metadata, publishing manuscripts on open online resources, and open-source code. In these areas, awareness could be increased through additional training in contexts where the specific practices are relevant. Individuals with more experience working and publishing might require less additional training, but might rather be motivated by further reforms of research assessment or the introduction of some other incentives.

Additionally, institutions should strive to create a more transparent and supportive environment for addressing and reporting misconduct, especially to reduce the prevalence of severe misconduct, such as plagiarism and fabrication. This may involve developing clearer policies and communication strategies and ensuring that all members of the academic community are familiar with these guidelines. Students, especially at earlier stages in their education, might also benefit from more extensive teaching on principles of academic integrity, such as citation practices. A shared approach to these developments across Ukrainian institutions would likely have benefits in terms of increased capacity and the ability to evaluate success in a consistent manner.

Promoting OS and academic integrity at Ukrainian HEIs must be a common effort, but approaches should be tailored to relevant stakeholders to achieve substantive impact. The relevance of various aspects of OS and academic integrity might differ between roles or disciplines. For example, students might be less affected by developments around publications, while research staff might be less concerned with use of unauthorised aims in exams. Efforts to promote OS and academic integrity should therefore engage with those who are already involved in relevant processes or will be in the future.

Future iterations of this survey, meanwhile, should aim to address the limitations identified here by employing a more rigorous longitudinal design to track individual changes over time. Researchers should consider strategies to differentiate repeat participants from new respondents, which would allow for more accurate trend analysis. Additionally, future surveys could benefit from clearer phrasing of questions, particularly regarding specific OS practices and academic integrity issues, to minimise “don’t know” responses and enhance data validity. This could be complemented by using comprehensive pre-tests with the target population, such as cognitive interviews, to further improve the survey instrument. However, to ensure comparability of future results to these findings, phrasing should be kept as consistent as possible. Extensions of the survey instrument might yield additional insights, such as inquiring about OS behaviours in addition to attitudes or include questions about the respondents’ individual behaviours. Finally, using a more representative sampling strategy, such as random sampling or stratified sampling based on demographics, while at the same time maintaining a high response rate among the sampled individuals, could also help improve the generalizability of the findings.

6. Bibliography

- Abdi, S., Pizzolato, D., Nemery, B., & Dierickx, K. (2021). Educating PhD Students in Research Integrity in Europe. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 27(1), 5. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-021-00290-0>
- Abele-Brehm, A. E., Gollwitzer, M., Steinberg, U., & Schönbrodt, F. D. (2019). Attitudes Toward Open Science and Public Data Sharing. *Social Psychology*, 50(4), 252–260. <https://doi.org/10.1027/1864-9335/a000384>
- About Institute for Open Science and Innovation | Institute for Open Science and Innovation. (2023). <https://openscience.org.ua/about>
- ALLEA - All European Academies. (2023). *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity*. ALLEA - All European Academies. <https://doi.org/10.26356/ECOC>
- Allum, N., Reid, A., Bidoglia, M., Gaskell, G., Aubert-Bonn, N., Buljan, I., Fuglsang, S., Horbach, S., Kavouras, P., Marušić, A., Mejlgard, N., Pizzolato, D., Roje, R., Tjldink, J., & Veltri, G. (2023). Researchers on research integrity: A survey of European and American researchers. *F1000Research*, 12, 187. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.128733.1>
- Armond, A. C. V., Gordijn, B., Lewis, J., Hosseini, M., Bodnár, J. K., Holm, S., & Kakuk, P. (2021). A scoping review of the literature featuring research ethics and research integrity cases. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 22(1), 50. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-021-00620-8>
- Berezko, O., Medina, L. M. P., Malaguarnera, G., Almeida, I., Żyra, A., Seang, S., Björnmalm, M., Hnatkova, E., & Tata, M. (2021). Perspectives on Open Science and Scholarly Publishing: A Survey Study Focusing on Early Career Researchers in Europe. *F1000Research*, 10, 1306. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.74831.1>
- Berezko, O., Reichmann, S., Artyukhov, A., Kuchma, I., Tsiatkovska, A., Zhezhnych, P., Chernov, A., Cophignon, A., Degtyarova, I., Herasymchuk, H., Khadzhynov, I., Krakovska, S., Krasnoshchok, O., Mozolevych, G., Oriekhova, T., Pnyovska, O., Ross-Hellauer, T., Wodo, W., & Zhylytsova, S. (2024). *2023 Results of Complex Academic Integrity and Open Science Surveys of OPTIMA Project* [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11180027>
- Berezko, O., Reichmann, S., Artyukhov, A., Kuchma, I., Tsiatkovska, A., Zhezhnych, P., Chernov, A., Cophignon, A., Degtyarova, I., Herasymchuk, H., Khadzhynov, I., Krakovska, S., Krasnoshchok, O., Mozolevych, G., Oriekhova, T., Pnyovska, O., Ross-Hellauer, T., Wojciech, W., & Svitlana, Z. (2022). *2022 Results of Complex Academic Integrity and Open Science Surveys of OPTIMA Project* [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8067262>
- Berezko, O., Reichmann, S., Artyukhov, A., Kuchma, I., Tsiatkovska, A., Zhezhnych, P., Chernov, A., Cophignon, A., Degtyarova, I., Herasymchuk, H., Khadzhynov, I., Krakovska, S., Mozolevych, G., Pnyovska, O., Ross-Hellauer, T., Wodo, W., & Zhylytsova, S. (2021). *2021 Results of Complex Academic Integrity and Open Science Surveys of OPTIMA Project* [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.8067081>

- Bouter, L. (2020). What Research Institutions Can Do to Foster Research Integrity. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 26(4), 2363–2369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-020-00178-5>
- Campbell, C., & Waddington, L. (2024). Academic Integrity Strategies: Student Insights. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 22(1), 33–50. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-024-09510-1>
- Childers, D., & Bruton, S. (2016). “Should It Be Considered Plagiarism?” Student Perceptions of Complex Citation Issues. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 14(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-015-9250-6>
- Christensen, G., Wang, Z., Levy Paluck, E., Swanson, N., Birke, D., Miguel, E., & Littman, R. (2020). *Open Science Practices are on the Rise: The State of Social Science (3S) Survey*. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0hx0207r>
- Cole, N. L., Kormann, E., Klebel, T., Apartis, S., & Ross-Hellauer, T. (2024). The societal impact of Open Science: A scoping review. *Royal Society Open Science*, 11(6), 240286. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.240286>
- De Peuter, S., Dierickx, K., Meganck, M., Lerouge, I., Vandeveld, W., & Storms, G. (2024). Mismatch in perceptions of the quality of supervision and research data management as an area of concern: Results from a university-wide survey of the research integrity culture at a Belgian university. *Accountability in Research*, 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2024.2318245>
- Digital Science, Hahnel, M., Smith, G., Schoenenberger, H., Scaplehorn, N., & Day, L. (2023). *The State of Open Data 2023*. Digital Science. <https://doi.org/10.6084/M9.FIGSHARE.24428194.V1>
- Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission). (2016a). *H2020 Programme—Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020*. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-data-mgt_en.pdf
- Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission). (2016b). *Open innovation, open science, open to the world: A vision for Europe*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/061652>
- Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission). (2017). *H2020 Programme—Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020*. https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf
- Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission). (2024). *Horizon Europe (Horizon)—HE Programme Guide*. https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf
- Directory of Open Access Journals – DOAJ*. (2024, June 26). <https://doaj.org/>

- Duliba, Y., Petroye, O., Pletsan, K., Havryliuk, A., Antonenko, V., & Antonova, O. (2022). Academic Integrity in Higher Educational Institutions in Times of the Covid-19 Pandemic: World Experience and Ukrainian Realities. *Revista Romaneasca Pentru Educatie Multidimensionala*, 14(4 Sup.1), 01–17. <https://doi.org/10.18662/rrem/14.4Sup1/656>
- Easterbrook, S. M. (2014). Open code for open science? *Nature Geoscience*, 7(11), 779–781. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2283>
- EOSC Association. (2022). Tripartite Collaboration—Ukraine. *EOSC Association*. <https://eosc.eu/tripartite-collaboration/ukraine/>
- Erçin Kamburoğlu, N., & Razi, S. (2024). Academic Misconduct Epidemic in Pandemic: Institutional Academic Integrity Promotion in Online Education. *Journal of Academic Ethics*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-024-09534-7>
- Fanelli, D. (2009). How Many Scientists Fabricate and Falsify Research? A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Survey Data. *PLOS ONE*, 4(5), e5738. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0005738>
- Fecher, B., & Friesike, S. (2014). Open Science: One Term, Five Schools of Thought. In *Opening Science: The Evolving Guide on How the Internet is Changing Research, Collaboration and Scholarly Publishing*. http://book.openingscience.org.s3.amazonaws.com/basics_background/open_science_one_term_five_schools_of_thought.html
- Ferguson, J., Littman, R., Christensen, G., Paluck, E. L., Swanson, N., Wang, Z., Miguel, E., Birke, D., & Pezzuto, J.-H. (2023). Survey of open science practices and attitudes in the social sciences. *Nature Communications*, 14(1), 5401. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41111-1>
- Gopalakrishna, G., Riet, G. ter, Vink, G., Stoop, I., Wicherts, J. M., & Bouter, L. M. (2022). Prevalence of questionable research practices, research misconduct and their potential explanatory factors: A survey among academic researchers in The Netherlands. *PLOS ONE*, 17(2), e0263023. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0263023>
- Gopalakrishna, G., Wicherts, J. M., Vink, G., Stoop, I., van den Akker, O. R., ter Riet, G., & Bouter, L. M. (2022). Prevalence of responsible research practices among academics in The Netherlands. *F1000Research*, 11, 471. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.110664.2>
- Government of Ukraine. (2022). *Government Resolution 'On Approval of the National Plan regarding Open Science,' No. 892-r*. <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/go/892-2022-%D1%80>
- Gruenhagen, J. H., Sinclair, P. M., Carroll, J.-A., Baker, P. R. A., Wilson, A., & Demant, D. (2024). The rapid rise of generative AI and its implications for academic integrity: Students' perceptions and use of chatbots for assistance with assessments. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 7, 100273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2024.100273>
- Harpe, S. E. (2024). *A Survey of Open Science Attitudes and Behaviors among US Pharmacy Faculty* (p. 2024.06.20.24309260). medRxiv. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.06.20.24309260>

- Havemann, L. (2016). Open Educational Resources. In M. A. Peters (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Educational Philosophy and Theory* (pp. 1–7). Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-287-532-7_218-1
- Haven, T., Gopalakrishna, G., Tjink, J., van der Schot, D., & Bouter, L. (2022). Promoting trust in research and researchers: How open science and research integrity are intertwined. *BMC Research Notes*, *15*(1), 302. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-022-06169-y>
- Hofmann, B., & Holm, S. (2019). Research integrity: Environment, experience, or ethos? *Research Ethics*, *15*(3–4), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1747016119880844>
- Hofmann, B., Thoresen, M., & Holm, S. (2023). Research Integrity Attitudes and Behaviors are Difficult to alter: Results from a ten Year Follow-up Study in Norway. *Journal of Empirical Research on Human Research Ethics*, *18*(1–2), 50–57. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15562646221150032>
- Kaiser, M., Drivdal, L., Hjellbrekke, J., Ingierd, H., & Rekdal, O. B. (2021). Questionable Research Practices and Misconduct Among Norwegian Researchers. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, *28*(1), 2. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-021-00351-4>
- Kaliuzhna, N., & Hauschke, C. (2024). Open access in Ukraine: Characteristics and evolution from 2012 to 2021. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1–20. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00324
- Klebel, T., Traag, V., Grypari, I., Stoy, L., & Ross-Hellauer, T. (2024). *The academic impact of Open Science: A scoping review*. OSF. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/ptjub>
- Koblianska, I., & Kostetska, I. (2023). SKILLS AND NEEDS OF THE REPRESENTATIVES OF THE UKRAINIAN ACADEMIC COMMUNITY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE OPEN SCIENCE CONCEPT. *Continuing Professional Education: Theory and Practice*, *77*(4), 42–54. <https://doi.org/10.28925/1609-8595.2023.4.4>
- Kormann, E., Klebel, T., Berezko, O., Zhezhnych, P., & Ross-Hellauer, T. (2024). *Code and Data for 'Report on academic integrity awareness and Open Science recognition levels in Ukraine (2021-2023)'* (Version v1.0.0) [Computer software]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13861182>
- Landau, W. M. (2021). The targets R package: A dynamic Make-like function-oriented pipeline toolkit for reproducibility and high-performance computing. *Journal of Open Source Software*, *6*(57), 2959. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.02959>
- Liut, M., Ly, A., Xu, J. J.-N., Banson, J., Vrbik, P., & Hardin, C. D. (2024). 'I Didn't Know': Examining Student Understanding of Academic Dishonesty in Computer Science. *Proceedings of the 55th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education V. 1*, 757–763. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3626252.3630753>
- Lugovyi, V., Drach, I., Petroye, O., Zinchenko, V., Melkow, Y., Zhyliaiev, I., Regeylo, I., Kamyshyn, V., & Bazeliuk, N. (2022). *Analysis of the leading domestic and foreign experience in enhancing the research capacity of Ukrainian universities under the war and post-war reconstruction circumstances in the context of the implementation of the Open Science concept* (V. Lugovyi & O. Petroye, Eds.). Institute of Higher Education of the National Academy of Pedagogical Sciences of Ukraine. <https://doi.org/10.31874/978-617-7644-57-5-2022>

- Luniachek, V., Brovdii, A., Kulakovskiy, O., & Varenko, T. (2020). Academic Integrity in Higher Education of Ukraine: Current State and Call for Action. *Education Research International*, 2020(1), 8856251. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8856251>
- Mabou Tagne, A., Cassina, N., Furgiuele, A., Storelli, E., Cosentino, M., & Marino, F. (2020). Perceptions and Attitudes about Research Integrity and Misconduct: A Survey among Young Biomedical Researchers in Italy. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 18(2), 193–205. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-020-09359-0>
- Macfarlane, B., Zhang, J., & Pun, A. (2014). Academic integrity: A review of the literature. *Studies in Higher Education*, 39(2), 339–358. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2012.709495>
- McFadden, D. (1974). Conditional logit analysis of qualitative choice behavior. In *Frontiers in econometrics* (pp. 105–142).
- Moher, D., Bouter, L., Kleinert, S., Glasziou, P., Sham, M. H., Barbour, V., Coriat, A.-M., Foeger, N., & Dirnagl, U. (2020). The Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers: Fostering research integrity. *PLOS Biology*, 18(7), e3000737. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000737>
- Molnar, K. K., & Kletke, M. G. (2012). Does the Type of Cheating Influence Undergraduate Students' Perceptions of Cheating? *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 10(3), 201–212. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-012-9164-5>
- Murray-Rust, P. (2008). Open Data in Science. *Nature Precedings*, 1–1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/npre.2008.1526.1>
- National Repository of Academic Texts. (2024). *National Repository of Academic Texts*. <https://nrat.ukrintei.ua/en/korysni-resursy/>
- Newton, P. M., & Essex, K. (2024). How Common is Cheating in Online Exams and did it Increase During the COVID-19 Pandemic? A Systematic Review. *Journal of Academic Ethics*, 22(2), 323–343. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10805-023-09485-5>
- Ni, R., & Waltman, L. (2024). To preprint or not to preprint: A global researcher survey. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 75(6), 749–766. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24880>
- Nosek, B. (2019). *Strategy for Culture Change*. <https://www.cos.io/blog/strategy-for-culture-change>
- OECD. (2015). *Making Open Science a Reality* (OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers No. 25; OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers, Vol. 25). OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5jrs2f963zs1-en>
- OECD. (2017). *OECD Reviews of Integrity in Education: Ukraine 2017*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264270664-en>
- OECD. (2021). *Open science—Enabling discovery in the digital age* (Going Digital Toolkit Notes No. 13; Going Digital Toolkit Notes, Vol. 13). OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/81a9dcf0-en>

Open4UA | Lviv Polytechnic National University. (2023). <https://lpnu.ua/en/open4ua>

OPTIMA | Lviv Polytechnic National University. (2021). <https://lpnu.ua/en/optima>

Pontika, N., Klebel, T., Correia, A., Metzler, H., Knoth, P., & Ross-Hellauer, T. (2022). Indicators of research quality, quantity, openness, and responsibility in institutional review, promotion, and tenure policies across seven countries. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 3(4), 888–911. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00224

Porkuian, O., Tselishchev, O., Halhash, R., Ivchenko, Y., & Khandii, O. (2023). Twice displaced, but unconquered: The experience of reviving a Ukrainian university during the war. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 21(2), 98–105. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21\(2-si\).2023.12](https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21(2-si).2023.12)

Pownall, M., Terry, J., Collins, E., Sladekova, M., & Jones, A. (2023). UK Psychology PhD researchers' knowledge, perceptions, and experiences of open science. *Cogent Psychology*, 10(1), 2248765. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311908.2023.2248765>

Pupovac, V., & Fanelli, D. (2015). Scientists Admitting to Plagiarism: A Meta-analysis of Surveys. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 21(5), 1331–1352. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-014-9600-6>

R Core Team. (2024). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>

Ravn, T., & Sørensen, M. P. (2021). Exploring the Gray Area: Similarities and Differences in Questionable Research Practices (QRPs) Across Main Areas of Research. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 27(4), 40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-021-00310-z>

Resnik, D. B., & Shamo, A. E. (2011). The Singapore Statement on Research Integrity. *Accountability in Research*, 18(2), 71–75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2011.557296>

Ross-Hellauer, T. (2017). What is open peer review? A systematic review. *F1000Research*, 6, 588. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.11369.2>

Ross-Hellauer, T., Deppe, A., & Schmidt, B. (2017). Survey on open peer review: Attitudes and experience amongst editors, authors and reviewers. *PLOS ONE*, 12(12), e0189311. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0189311>

Ross-Hellauer, T., Klebel, T., Knoth, P., & Pontika, N. (2024). Value dissonance in research(er) assessment: Individual and perceived institutional priorities in review, promotion, and tenure. *Science and Public Policy*, 51(3), 337–351. <https://doi.org/10.1093/scipol/scad073>

Ross-Hellauer, T., Reichmann, S., Cole, N. L., Fessler, A., Klebel, T., & Pontika, N. (2022). Dynamics of cumulative advantage and threats to equity in open science: A scoping review. *Royal Society Open Science*, 9(1), 211032. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.211032>

Rowley, J., Johnson, F., Scaffi, L., Frass, W., & Devine, E. (2017). Academics' behaviors and attitudes towards open access publishing in scholarly journals. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 68(5), 1201–1211. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23710>

- Rudis, B. (2024). *ggchicklet: Create Chicklet (Rounded Segmented Column) Charts* [HTML]. <https://github.com/hrbrmstr/ggchicklet> (Original work published 2019)
- Schneider, J. W., Allum, N., Andersen, J. P., Petersen, M. B., Madsen, E. B., Mejlgard, N., & Zachariae, R. (2024). Is something rotten in the state of Denmark? Cross-national evidence for widespread involvement but not systematic use of questionable research practices across all fields of research. *PLOS ONE*, *19*(8), e0304342. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0304342>
- Schöpfel, J., Ferrant, C., André, F., & Fabre, R. (2016). Ready for the future? A survey on open access with scientists from the French National Research Center (CNRS). *Interlending & Document Supply*, *44*(4), 141–149. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ILDS-06-2016-0023>
- Sciences, N. R. C. (US) C. on R. of A. in the B. (2003). Sharing Materials Integral to Published Findings. In *Sharing Publication-Related Data and Materials: Responsibilities of Authorship in the Life Sciences*. National Academies Press (US). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK97159/>
- Shaw, D., & Satalkar, P. (2018). Researchers' interpretations of research integrity: A qualitative study. *Accountability in Research*, *25*(2), 79–93. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2017.1413940>
- Shevchenko, V., Malysh, N., & Tkachuk-Miroshnychenko, O. (2024). Distance learning in Ukraine in COVID-19 emergency. *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and e-Learning*, *39*(1), 4–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680513.2021.1967115>
- Soderberg, C. K., Errington, T. M., & Nosek, B. A. (2020). Credibility of preprints: An interdisciplinary survey of researchers. *Royal Society Open Science*, *7*(10), 201520. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.201520>
- Stukalo, N., & Simakhova, A. (2020). COVID-19 Impact on Ukrainian Higher Education. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, *8*(8), 3673–3678. <https://doi.org/10.13189/ujer.2020.080846>
- Suber, P. (2012). *Open Access*. The MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/9286.001.0001>
- UNESCO. (2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54677/MNMMH8546>
- UNESCO & Canadian National Commission for UNESCO. (2022). *An introduction to the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. UNESCO. <https://doi.org/10.54677/XOIR1696>
- Vicente-Saez, R., & Martinez-Fuentes, C. (2018). Open Science now: A systematic literature review for an integrated definition. *Journal of Business Research*, *88*, 428–436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.12.043>
- Vlashenko, L. G., Gryschenko, T. B., & Nikitenko, O. M. (2021). *Open Science in Technical University*. <https://openarchive.nure.ua/handle/document/18618>
- Wickham, H. (2016). *Ggplot2*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-24277-4>

- Wickham, H., Averick, M., Bryan, J., Chang, W., McGowan, L. D., François, R., Golemund, G., Hayes, A., Henry, L., Hester, J., Kuhn, M., Pedersen, T. L., Miller, E., Bache, S. M., Müller, K., Ooms, J., Robinson, D., Seidel, D. P., Spinu, V., ... Yutani, H. (2019). Welcome to the Tidyverse. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 4(43), 1686. <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.01686>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, Ij. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Xie, Y., Wang, K., & Kong, Y. (2021). Prevalence of Research Misconduct and Questionable Research Practices: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 27(4), 41. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-021-00314-9>
- Young, R. L. (2012). *Don't Know Responses in Survey Research* [Pennsylvania State University]. <https://etda.libraries.psu.edu/catalog/13934>
- Zakharova, O., & Prodanova, L. (2023). A university displaced twice: Irreversible and erroneous losses of human capital. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 21(2), 123–132. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21\(2-si\).2023.15](https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21(2-si).2023.15)
- Zečević, K., Houghton, C., Noone, C., Lee, H., Matvienko-Sikar, K., & Toomey, E. (2021). Exploring factors that influence the practice of Open Science by early career health researchers: A mixed methods study. *HRB Open Research*, 3, 56. <https://doi.org/10.12688/hrbopenres.13119.2>
- Zhao, L., Peng, J., Yang, X., Yan, W., Ke, S., Batool, K., Li, Y., & Lee, K. (2024). Effects of academic dishonesty policy reminder on university students' exam cheating – a double-blind randomized controlled experimental field study. *Studies in Higher Education*, 49(4), 592–608. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2023.2246073>
- Zhelnin, V., & Havryliuk, M. (2024). *Draft law on academic integrity: What does it envision, and how would it operate?* <https://voxukraine.org/en/draft-law-on-academic-integrity-what-does-it-envision-and-how-would-it-operate>

7. Appendices

A. Survey Instrument

The survey contained items of two types, differing in their respective instructions and response categories:

1. Agreement: “To what extent do you agree with the following statements?”
 - a. “strongly agree”
 - b. “rather agree”
 - c. “rather disagree”
 - d. “strongly disagree”
 - e. “don’t know”
2. Frequency:
 - a. “very often”
 - b. “frequently”
 - c. “sometimes”
 - d. “rarely”
 - e. “never”
 - f. “don’t know”

Table A. 1. Survey items in their order of presentation with topical group and item instruction type.

	Item Text	Topical Group	Item Type
Q15	Overall, the processes at my higher education institution are organised in a clear and transparent manner	Institution/ Administration	Agreement
Q16	The quality of educational services at my higher education institution is high	Education	Agreement
Q17	Researchers should publish all research results (both positive and negative)	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Agreement
Q18	All co-authors are fully responsible for the content of the publication, regardless of the amount of their contribution	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Agreement
Q19	Changes to experimental data after the end of the experiment are acceptable	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Agreement
Q20	It is necessary to indicate the authorship of all those who have contributed to the research without exception	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Agreement
Q21	Researchers should report any conflicts of interest when publishing research results and applying for funding	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Agreement
Q22	Students should openly publish the full texts of their diploma theses	Education	Agreement
Q23	Students must understand what constitutes inappropriate academic behavior and report it to the appropriate authorities	Education	Agreement
Q24	Using other author's published papers and ideas without proper reference to the original source.	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Frequency
Q25	The author uses his own previous publications as part of a new work without proper acknowledgment or citation of the original.	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Frequency
Q26	Making up data or facts about a scientific activity, for example, a research experiment.	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Frequency
Q27	Selective citations to support one's conclusions or to please editors, reviewers, colleagues, etc.	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Frequency
Q28	The author passes off other people's academic achievements as his own.	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Frequency

Q29	A person attributes to himself or herself the authorship of a work (assignment, article, etc.) that he or she did not actually perform, but arranged for others to perform it for a fee or in another way.	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Frequency
Q30	Students help each other during exams or tests.	Education	Frequency
Q31	Students use cheat sheets, smartphones, or other means of cheating during exams or tests.	Education	Frequency
Q32	Students and teachers use unauthorized software (so-called "pirated software").	Education	Frequency
Q33	Incitement to violate academic integrity.	Institution/ Administration	Frequency
Q34	The administration of the institution tolerates cases of academic dishonesty.	Institution/ Administration	Frequency
Q35	Falsely accusing a student or employee of misconduct or other violations.	Institution/ Administration	Frequency
Q36	Abuse of official position or authority to encourage academic dishonesty.	Institution/ Administration	Frequency
Q37	The university administration accuses and punishes whistleblowers of academic integrity violations.	Institution/ Administration	Frequency
Q38	Research results should be in open access, i.e. freely available to the academic community and the general public.	Open Science	Agreement
Q39	Research papers should be openly available even before the official peer review process, i.e. before a thorough review of their content.	Open Science	Agreement
Q40	Authors should retain intellectual property rights to their published works, even at the cost of giving up some opportunities for free publication	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Agreement
Q41	Scholars should explain the results of their research to the general public in an understandable way.	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Agreement
Q42	Researchers should publish author's versions of manuscripts on open online resources such as Zenodo, institutional repositories, etc.	Open Science	Agreement
Q43	Researchers should invest time in describing their experimental data with appropriate metadata so that the data can be easily found and reused.	Open Science	Agreement
Q44	Time should be invested in describing research methodology, tools, and experimental results in detail so that other researchers can reproduce them.	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Agreement
Q45	Experimental data should be published as openly as possible.	Open Science	Agreement
Q46	If software development is part of a research project, the source code should be published alongside the relevant scientific papers.	Open Science	Agreement
Q47	Researchers should always strive to ensure that their research serves a broad public purpose, regardless of the field of science in which they work.	Reporting and Academic Integrity	Agreement
Q48	The names of peer reviewers of research papers should be made public, regardless of whether their conclusion is positive or negative.	Open Science	Agreement
Q49	The texts of positive and negative peer reviews of research papers should be published alongside these papers.	Open Science	Agreement
Q50	Authors of research papers and peer reviewers should be able to communicate directly without intermediaries.	Open Science	Agreement
Q51	Higher education institutions should provide open access to their educational resources (textbooks, manuals, various digital tools, etc.) for everyone.	Education	Agreement
Q52	I can explain what "open science" is.	Open Science	Agreement

B. Additional Demographic Characteristics

Table B. 1. Gender distribution within the sample by survey year.

Gender	2021	2022	2023
female	66.2% (6,090)	61.9% (6,007)	64.4% (3,731)
male	33.3% (3,063)	37.5% (3,636)	34.8% (2,017)
other	0.5% (50)	0.7% (65)	0.8% (46)

Table B. 2. Distribution of different roles/groups at HEIs within the sample by survey year.

Academic Role	2021	2022	2023
student - 1st year	14.5% (1,337)	17.5% (1,697)	10.1% (584)
student - 2nd year	12.1% (1,118)	14.2% (1,383)	8.8% (507)
student - 3rd year	8.7% (797)	13.7% (1,326)	8.4% (486)
student - 4th year	7.6% (701)	10.0% (970)	8.1% (471)
master student	7.6% (703)	9.3% (903)	11.9% (691)
doctoral student - PhD	5.0% (458)	3.1% (298)	5.9% (342)
doctoral student - ScD (higher doctorate)	0.5% (44)	0.4% (37)	0.4% (24)
faculty	35.9% (3,307)	26.0% (2,522)	37.1% (2,150)
research staff	1.3% (118)	2.2% (216)	2.0% (113)
university administrator	2.1% (193)	1.5% (150)	2.7% (156)
librarian	2.4% (223)	0.9% (84)	1.6% (90)
other	2.2% (204)	1.3% (122)	3.1% (180)

Table B. 3. Distribution of highest obtained degree within the sample by survey year.

Highest Obtained Degree	2021	2022	2023
none (still studying)	40.5% (3,731)	52.5% (5,100)	32.9% (1,906)
bachelor	10.6% (973)	11.2% (1,083)	13.4% (779)
master	12.5% (1,150)	9.8% (947)	16.1% (932)
PhD	27.2% (2,499)	19.9% (1,932)	27.4% (1,590)
ScD (higher doctorate)	9.2% (850)	6.7% (646)	10.1% (587)

Table B. 4. Distribution of number of publications published within the last 3 years within the sample by survey year.

Number of Publications (last 3 years)	2021	2022	2023
0	39.9% (3,673)	53.2% (5,165)	34.4% (1,996)
1-5	22.8% (2,094)	20.0% (1,945)	27.3% (1,581)
6-10	13.8% (1,268)	10.6% (1,026)	15.2% (880)
11-20	12.6% (1,159)	8.7% (846)	12.2% (707)
21-30	4.8% (443)	3.2% (313)	4.8% (281)
more than 30	6.2% (566)	4.3% (413)	6.0% (349)

Table B. 5. Distribution of number of peer review reports written within the last 3 years within the sample by survey year.

Number of Peer Review Reports (last 3 years)	2021	2022	2023
0	62.1% (5,716)	71.4% (6,929)	59.9% (3,471)
1-5	24.3% (2,237)	19.9% (1,934)	26.9% (1,558)
6-10	7.4% (677)	5.0% (481)	6.8% (393)
11-20	3.4% (309)	2.3% (219)	3.7% (216)
21-30	1.3% (120)	0.7% (67)	0.9% (53)
more than 30	1.6% (144)	0.8% (78)	1.8% (103)

Table B. 6. Distribution of work experience in higher education or research within the sample by survey year.

Number of Years Working in Higher Education/Research	2021	2022	2023
I have never worked in this sphere	47.6% (4,379)	61.8% (5,998)	46.3% (2,682)
less than 1 year	3.5% (323)	2.4% (229)	2.9% (168)
1-5 years	7.4% (682)	5.4% (525)	6.4% (372)
5-10 years	5.9% (542)	3.9% (378)	5.4% (312)
more than 10 years	35.6% (3,277)	26.6% (2,578)	39.0% (2,260)

Table B. 7. Distribution of respondents' type of HEI by survey year.

Type of Institution	2021	2022	2023
technical	20.8% (1,912)	28.3% (2,745)	29.5% (1,710)
classical	19.3% (1,780)	20.7% (2,005)	24.1% (1,399)
pedagogical	16.5% (1,517)	14.0% (1,363)	16.8% (975)
military and internal security (army, police, civil defense, etc.)	13.9% (1,282)	6.1% (596)	5.5% (316)
agricultural	4.1% (377)	8.2% (797)	4.7% (274)
medical	7.3% (668)	5.2% (506)	4.6% (268)
economical	3.9% (363)	4.1% (402)	3.1% (180)
law	4.2% (390)	3.0% (294)	3.5% (201)
humanitarian	2.2% (203)	2.2% (212)	1.7% (101)
pharmaceutical	3.0% (277)	0.6% (55)	0.2% (11)
artistic	1.2% (114)	1.1% (103)	0.9% (53)
physical education and sports	0.4% (39)	0.9% (84)	0.6% (32)
cultural	0.1% (12)	0.2% (21)	0.2% (11)
theological	0.1% (10)	0.1% (5)	0.2% (10)
other	2.8% (259)	5.4% (520)	4.4% (253)

Table B. 8. Distribution of respondents' indicated fields/disciplines by survey year.

Field/Discipline	2021	2022	2023
Education/pedagogy	15.9% (1,462)	12.4% (1,200)	15.3% (885)
Law	12.4% (1,145)	7.5% (728)	10.2% (592)
Social and behavioral sciences	9.5% (878)	9.1% (886)	8.5% (493)
Information technology	6.6% (605)	11.1% (1,081)	8.2% (478)
Humanities	8.2% (752)	6.1% (590)	9.0% (522)
Health care	9.5% (871)	6.5% (633)	5.5% (317)
Management and administration	4.7% (428)	5.0% (484)	5.5% (319)
Natural sciences	3.4% (309)	3.1% (302)	3.2% (188)
Culture and art	2.8% (256)	2.5% (245)	3.2% (185)
Agricultural and food sciences	1.9% (173)	4.0% (386)	1.8% (105)
Mechanical engineering	1.7% (154)	3.5% (339)	2.9% (170)
Architecture and construction	2.0% (186)	3.1% (304)	2.6% (151)
Chemical and bioengineering	2.5% (234)	2.1% (208)	3.2% (183)
Production and technology	1.5% (142)	2.9% (281)	2.4% (140)
Public management and administration	1.9% (178)	2.6% (253)	2.1% (121)
Mathematics and statistics	1.8% (169)	2.1% (202)	2.0% (118)
Military sciences, national security, state border security	2.6% (238)	2.1% (203)	0.8% (44)
Biology	2.0% (185)	2.0% (197)	1.7% (101)
Electrical engineering	1.2% (113)	2.0% (193)	1.8% (105)
Transportation	1.0% (91)	2.4% (231)	1.5% (88)
Service industry	0.9% (81)	1.7% (163)	1.4% (83)
Automation and instrumentation	1.2% (107)	1.2% (113)	1.7% (97)
Social work	1.1% (102)	1.2% (115)	1.5% (89)
Electronics and telecommunications	1.1% (100)	1.3% (126)	1.3% (78)
Veterinary medicine	0.8% (73)	0.8% (80)	0.9% (51)
Civil security	1.1% (102)	0.7% (64)	0.6% (36)
Journalism	0.6% (56)	0.9% (91)	0.8% (46)
Theology	0.1% (13)	0.1% (10)	0.2% (9)

Table B. 9. Proportions of respondents of the 2022 survey by answers to the question “Have you been an internally displaced person (within Ukraine) from 24.02.2022 to the present day?”.

	%	n
no	75.0	7,278
yes	24.7	2,395

Table B. 10. Proportions of respondents of the 2022 survey by answers to the question “Have you been a refugee abroad from 24.02.2022 to the present day?”.

	%	n
no	86.7	8,414
yes	12.8	1,246

Table B. 11. Proportions of respondents of the 2022 survey by answers to the question “Where are you now?”.

	%	n
at home on the territory controlled by Ukraine	74.7	7,248
at home on the temporarily occupied territory	1.9	182
in another region of Ukraine (internally displaced person)	12.3	1,195
abroad as a refugee	7.1	688
other	4.0	384

Table B. 12. Proportions of respondents of the 2022 national survey by answers to the question “Was your higher education institution in the area of hostilities or under temporary occupation after 24.02.2022?”.

	%	n
no	71.1	5,498
yes, now on the territory controlled by Ukraine	20.2	1,557
yes, still on the temporarily occupied territory	4.8	373
don't know	3.9	299

Table B. 13. Proportions of respondents of the 2022 national survey by answers to the question “Is your higher education institution a displaced one?”.

	%	n
no	84.0	6,488
yes, after the full-scale invasion in 2022	10.9	845
yes, after the start of the war in 2014	1.5	118
don't know	3.6	276

Figure B. 1. Absolute number of respondents per Oblast across the annual surveys.

C. Additional Results and Figures

Figure C. 1. Percentage point difference of “don’t know” answers compared to 2021 among respondents not yet holding a university degree.

Figure C. 2. Percentage point difference of “don’t know” answers compared to 2021 among respondents holding a university degree.

Table C. 1. Regression models to predict levels of agreement on OS statements by survey year.

ID	Item	% Agreement			2022 vs. 2021				2023 vs. 2022				McFadden's R ²
		2021	2022	2023	Beta	SE	z	p	Beta	SE	z	p	
Q38	Research results should be in open access, i.e. freely available to the academic community and the general public.	92.08	92.22	93.60	0.019	0.056	0.341	0.7332	0.230	0.068	3.379	0.0007	0.001
Q39	Research papers should be openly available even before the official peer review process, i.e. before a thorough review of their content.	36.89	35.86	44.86	-0.044	0.033	-1.360	0.1740	0.331	0.036	9.119	0.0000	0.004
Q42	Researchers should publish author's versions of manuscripts on open online resources such as Zenodo, institutional repositories, etc.	74.85	76.78	75.04	0.105	0.040	2.645	0.0082	0.010	0.043	0.228	0.8199	0.000
Q43	Researchers should invest time in describing their experimental data with appropriate metadata so that the data can be easily found and reused.	79.64	82.41	80.07	0.181	0.043	4.212	0.0000	0.026	0.047	0.566	0.5715	0.001
Q45	Experimental data should be published as openly as possible.	83.74	83.12	82.92	-0.045	0.043	-1.046	0.2955	-0.059	0.048	-1.218	0.2233	0.000
Q46	If software development is part of a research project, the source code should be published alongside the relevant scientific papers.	64.93	64.55	66.95	-0.017	0.037	-0.452	0.6510	0.090	0.041	2.189	0.0286	0.000
Q48	The names of peer reviewers of research papers should be made public, regardless of whether their conclusion is positive or negative.	81.62	84.39	80.08	0.197	0.042	4.673	0.0000	-0.100	0.045	-2.197	0.0280	0.002
Q49	The texts of positive and negative peer reviews of research papers should be published alongside these papers.	71.89	75.95	72.82	0.211	0.037	5.726	0.0000	0.046	0.041	1.146	0.2520	0.001
Q50	Authors of research papers and peer reviewers should be able to communicate directly without intermediaries.	75.64	80.00	75.66	0.253	0.039	6.447	0.0000	0.001	0.042	0.025	0.9797	0.002
Q52	I can explain what "open science" is.	89.67	86.49	87.56	-0.304	0.050	-6.041	0.0000	-0.210	0.057	-3.684	0.0002	0.003

Table C. 2. Regression models to predict levels of agreement on reporting and academic integrity statements by survey year.

ID	Item	% Agreement			2022 vs. 2021				2023 vs. 2022				McFadden's R ²
		2021	2022	2023	Beta	SE	z	p	Beta	SE	z	p	
Q17	Researchers should publish all research results (both positive and negative)	81.67	83.05	83.17	0.095	0.040	2.381	0.0173	0.103	0.045	2.270	0.0232	0.000
Q18	All co-authors are fully responsible for the content of the publication, regardless of the amount of their contribution	90.70	91.90	91.40	0.151	0.053	2.848	0.0044	0.085	0.060	1.430	0.1528	0.001
Q19	Changes to experimental data after the end of the experiment are acceptable	58.76	61.53	65.67	0.116	0.032	3.646	0.0003	0.295	0.037	8.045	0.0000	0.002
Q20	It is necessary to indicate the authorship of all those who have contributed to the research without exception	96.55	96.52	95.79	-0.009	0.081	-0.112	0.9104	-0.207	0.088	-2.358	0.0184	0.001
Q21	Researchers should report any conflicts of interest when publishing research results and applying for funding	87.76	86.90	90.21	-0.078	0.047	-1.680	0.0930	0.250	0.057	4.415	0.0000	0.002
Q40	Authors should retain intellectual property rights to their published works, even at the cost of giving up some opportunities for free publication	85.81	87.04	85.69	0.105	0.047	2.215	0.0268	-0.010	0.052	-0.189	0.8498	0.000
Q41	Scholars should explain the results of their research to the general public in an understandable way.	85.06	86.35	84.29	0.105	0.044	2.381	0.0173	-0.059	0.049	-1.220	0.2224	0.001
Q44	Time should be invested in describing research methodology, tools, and experimental results in detail so that other researchers can reproduce them.	79.11	80.57	80.94	0.091	0.041	2.195	0.0281	0.115	0.046	2.473	0.0134	0.000
Q47	Researchers should always strive to ensure that their research serves a broad public purpose, regardless of the field of science in which they work.	89.20	89.14	88.23	-0.007	0.051	-0.135	0.8923	-0.097	0.056	-1.734	0.0829	0.000

Table C. 3. Regression models to predict levels with which practices on reporting and academic integrity are reported as occurring often by survey year.

ID	Item	% Reported as often			2022 vs. 2021				2023 vs. 2022				McFadden's R ²
		2021	2022	2023	Beta	SE	z	p	Beta	SE	z	p	
Q24	Using other author's published papers and ideas without proper reference to the original source.	14.38	13.43	16.40	-0.080	0.051	-1.574	0.1154	0.155	0.054	2.849	0.0044	0.001
Q25	The author uses his own previous publications as part of a new work without proper acknowledgment or citation of the original.	16.22	14.75	19.36	-0.112	0.051	-2.196	0.0281	0.215	0.053	4.052	0.0001	0.003
Q26	Making up data or facts about a scientific activity, for example, a research experiment.	8.76	7.50	12.95	-0.170	0.070	-2.432	0.0150	0.438	0.069	6.376	0.0000	0.008
Q27	Selective citations to support one's conclusions or to please editors, reviewers, colleagues, etc.	18.19	17.50	21.74	-0.046	0.049	-0.940	0.3470	0.223	0.052	4.251	0.0000	0.002
Q28	The author passes off other people's academic achievements as his own.	7.72	6.68	11.96	-0.156	0.072	-2.160	0.0307	0.484	0.071	6.833	0.0000	0.009
Q29	A person attributes to himself or herself the authorship of a work (assignment, article, etc.) that he or she did not actually perform, but arranged for others to perform it for a fee or in another way.	14.54	13.12	17.11	-0.119	0.054	-2.203	0.0276	0.193	0.057	3.371	0.0008	0.002

Table C. 4. Regression models to predict levels of agreement on statements on education by survey year.

ID	Item	% Agreement			2022 vs. 2021				2023 vs. 2022				McFadden's R ²
		2021	2022	2023	Beta	SE	z	p	Beta	SE	z	p	
Q16	The quality of educational services at my higher education institution is high	88.48	86.56	88.31	-0.176	0.045	-3.941	0.0001	-0.017	0.053	-0.323	0.7469	0.001
Q22	Students should openly publish the full texts of their diploma theses	75.45	71.19	80.91	-0.218	0.035	-6.269	0.0000	0.322	0.043	7.524	0.0000	0.007
Q23	Students must understand what constitutes inappropriate academic behavior and report it to the appropriate authorities	94.04	94.19	94.87	0.027	0.064	0.416	0.6775	0.159	0.075	2.104	0.0353	0.000
Q51	Higher education institutions should provide open access to their educational resources (textbooks, manuals, various digital tools, etc.) for everyone.	78.62	81.45	79.07	0.178	0.039	4.577	0.0000	0.027	0.043	0.632	0.5271	0.001

Table C. 5. Regression models to predict levels with which practices within the educational context are reported as occurring often by survey year.

ID	Item	% Reported as often			2022 vs. 2021				2023 vs. 2022				McFadden's R ²
		2021	2022	2023	Beta	SE	z	p	Beta	SE	z	p	
Q30	Students help each other during exams or tests.	32.91	33.61	34.60	0.032	0.034	0.937	0.3489	0.076	0.038	1.965	0.0494	0.000
Q31	Students use cheat sheets, smartphones, or other means of cheating during exams or tests.	21.89	20.60	26.99	-0.077	0.039	-1.966	0.0493	0.277	0.043	6.500	0.0000	0.003
Q32	Students and teachers use unauthorized software (so-called "pirated software").	20.93	21.72	24.61	0.047	0.045	1.057	0.2904	0.210	0.049	4.297	0.0000	0.001

Table C. 6. Regression models to predict levels with which institutional/administrative practices are reported as occurring often by survey year.

ID	Item	% Reported as often			2022 vs. 2021				2023 vs. 2022				McFadden's R ²
		2021	2022	2023	Beta	SE	z	p	Beta	SE	z	p	
Q33	Incitement to violate academic integrity.	5.16	5.23	9.32	0.013	0.079	0.161	0.8717	0.636	0.078	8.145	0.0000	0.011
Q34	The administration of the institution tolerates cases of academic dishonesty.	11.54	10.90	14.37	-0.064	0.059	-1.087	0.2769	0.252	0.060	4.168	0.0000	0.002
Q35	Falsely accusing a student or employee of misconduct or other violations.	5.46	6.54	9.52	0.193	0.075	2.584	0.0098	0.600	0.077	7.804	0.0000	0.007
Q36	Abuse of official position or authority to encourage academic dishonesty.	7.06	7.73	11.79	0.098	0.068	1.437	0.1509	0.565	0.069	8.200	0.0000	0.008
Q37	The university administration accuses and punishes whistleblowers of academic integrity violations.	19.79	20.82	23.00	0.064	0.053	1.196	0.2318	0.191	0.056	3.398	0.0000	0.001

Table C. 7. Regression models to predict levels of agreement on statement about transparent and clear process at respondents' HEIs by survey year.

ID	Item	% Agreement			2022 vs. 2021				2023 vs. 2022				McFadden's R ²
		2021	2022	2023	Beta	SE	z	p	Beta	SE	z	p	
Q15	Overall, the processes at my higher education institution are organised in a clear and transparent manner	90.47	88.39	90.43	-0.22	0.048	-4.585	0.0000	-0.005	0.057	-0.089	0.9293	0.002

Figure C. 3. Extent of agreement with statements on OS by student subgroups (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 4. Extent of agreement with statements on OS by different survey populations (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 5. Extent of agreement with statements on OPR by different peer review experience (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 6. Extent of agreement with statements on reporting and academic integrity by student subgroups (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 7. Rates of questionable practices to occur often at the respondent’s HEI by student subgroups (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 8. Extent of agreement with statements on reporting and academic integrity by different survey populations (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 9. Rates of questionable practices to occur often at the respondent’s HEI by different survey populations (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 10. Extent of agreement with statements on education by student subgroups (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 11. Rates of practices to occur often in education at the respondent’s HEI by student subgroups (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 12. Extent of agreement with statements on education by different survey populations (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 13. Rates of practices to occur often in education at the respondent’s HEI by different survey populations (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 14. Rates of institutional/administrative practices to occur often at the respondent’s HEI by student subgroups (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 15. Extent of agreement with statement on processes being clear and transparent at the respondent’s HEI by student subgroups (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 16. Rates of institutional/administrative practices to occur often at the respondent’s HEI by different survey populations (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

Figure C. 17. Extent of agreement with statement on processes being clear and transparent at the respondent’s HEI by different survey populations (after exclusion of missing and “don’t know” responses).

